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Operationalization of Necropolitics in the United States' migration policies

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Abstract

In Necropolitics, fear of death as a unifying human experience is used as an instrument of sovereign obedience and social control – whence the agency’s sheer existence is dependent on the sovereign. This existential dread yields great political authority to sovereign offering protection in a form of refuge. Yet, the process of refuge and immigration masks a violent institutional reality that remains safe behind a humanitarian narrative of rescuing refugees. Through the exploration of the hidden institutional violence, this paper sought to find the meaning behind policies -as political artifacts- which constitute legislation. *Who created the policies? Why they were created? Who do they benefit?* Applied to the U.S.’s response to the migration of Afghans, this research utilizes interpretive policy analysis tools, this paper creates a framework for detecting possible bureaucratic entrapments in migration policies for Afghans, which are then used as technologies of control. This coalesces with the phenomenological ethnography of Afghan migrants, whose experience of undergoing migration and resettlement can bolster the realization of how Necropolitics is operationalized in the U.S.’s migration policies.

Аннотация

В Некрополитике страх смерти как объединяющий человеческий опыт используется как инструмент повиновения суверену и социального контроля - таким образом, само существование агентства зависит от суверена. Этот экзистенциальный страх дает большую политическую власть суверену, предлагающему защиту в форме убежища. Однако процесс предоставления убежища и иммиграции маскирует жестокую институциональную реальность, которая остается в безопасности за гуманитарным нарративом спасения беженцев. Исследуя скрытое институциональное насилие, в данной работе мы попытались найти смысл политики - как политического артефакта - которая представляет собой законодательство. Кто создал эти политики? Почему они были созданы? Кому они выгодны? Применительно к реакции США на миграцию афганцев, данное исследование использует инструменты интерпретативного анализа политики, создавая основу для выявления возможных бюрократических ловушек в миграционной политике для афганцев, которые затем используются как технологии контроля. Это сочетается с феноменологической этнографией афганских мигрантов, чей опыт миграции и переселения может способствовать осознанию того, как некрополитика реализуется в миграционной политике США.

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1. Introduction

The heart-wrenching footage of Afghan stowaways tumbling from the sky as they let go of the landing gears of the soaring C-17 will remain imprinted in the collective memory of scholars studying the politics of migration. Watching the footage from Afghanistan, provoked a cognitive dissonance in my mind: Having worked with Afghan migration centers in Malaysia, I understood the emotions, the rage, and the desperation of the Afghans praying for help. As a political scientist, I attempted to rationalize the U.S.'s evacuation process. The chase of hundreds of Afghans on the tarmac of the runway and the footage of men and women being stacked for evacuation from Afghanistan draws a familiar narrative to the older generations who reminisce the fall of Saigon – the footage of the Helicopters evacuating migrants from the U.S. Embassy.

Both scenes symbolize the chaotic end to the American occupation of a foreign territory. Yet, the facade of what they portray, is a humanitarian effort by a former invader/occupier, rescuing a swarm of pleading refugees. The transition of invader-to-saviour is an outrageously perplexing phenomenon, one which begs further scrutiny into the crux of migration. The intent of this research stems from my inability to rationalize the evacuation. What I observed and understood, is the clandestine violence behind the spurious humanitarian narrative of the evacuation.

My journey from being an ardent humanitarian to a critic of the U.S.'s rescue mission begins with the works of Achilles Mbembe, the Necropolitics, whose critique of colonial institutions has been a backbone of my anthropological studies of institutional violence. The narrative Mbembe draws on, asserts that Necropolitics exists as a phantom behind every humanitarian or dehumanizing decision in world politics. Its empirical exploration will utilize decision-makers with greater accountability and stronger consideration of dignified human sovereignty. Sprouting from the works of Mbembe, this research aims to find the parallels of how Necropolitical frameworks, exercised through legislations and policies, culminate in a humanitarian crisis within the migration.

Paradoxically, there is no formal written policy that legislates the enforcement of violence in a migration process for the benefit of the state. Ergo, the examination of a theory that reinforces this impression, requires an interpretive approach that scrutinizes the entrenched violence, and the intrinsic essences of policies. The essences constitute the broader context surrounding the policies – What do they mean? Why they were drafted? Who introduced them? Who benefits from them? An empirical study supplements the examination of the policies, by incorporating the factual and tangible outcomes of the policies from the field they're exerted in. To what extent the meaning presented by the policy conforms to its meaning in practice? If a policy enforces violence, how do we measure the violence?

This research deconstructs the operationalization of institutional violence –the necropolitics– within the U.S.’s migration policy. It builds a new paradigm to examine a broader spectrum of U.S.’s foreign policies, which with little mention of migration, contributes to a grand scheme of reinforcing the U.S.’s hegemonic status as the suzerain of the free world.

The tracing of how necropolitical policies are operationalized to bolster “hegemonic” contentions, begins with conceptualizing the relation between the U.S. government as the sovereign, and the refugee immigrants as the subjects of the sovereign. Given the limited scholarly consensus on what should be defined as a “refugee”, my work uses the conceptualization of “Survival Migrants” proposed by Betts.¹ Given the term’s lack of compatibility to fully capture the scope of this research, I incorporate its fundamental features in creating a convenient neologism that specifically suits the individuals subjected to necropolitical policies – the necropeon.

Next, with strong reference to the works of Fitzgerald² and Haddad³, we establish the codependent nature between the Sovereign and the Subjects, and the cluster of policies the sovereign uses to modulate its territories and consolidate its control within its internal and external territories. This section also strongly draws on the various policies used by the global North to contain and stall migration from the developing countries – policies which will echo strongly in the empirical section.

By drawing reference to the works of Davies⁴ on institutional violence of inaction and ineffective policies in the context of refugees in Calais, this paper explores the recent scholarly works within the necropolitical frameworks. We further discuss the gaps my research is ought to fill by taking a lead from Davies’ existing research.

This theory-driven research which contends to explore the unwritten meanings and institutions within migration policies, strongly utilizes the interpretive methods. The key theory of this research posits that Necropolitical frameworks in migration policy are operationalized through laboring the Necropeons for the sovereign’s consolidation. Chapter 3. Methodology deconstructs this theory, and justifies the employment of interpretative policy analysis, posthuman performativity, and phenomenological ethnography, as mediums to explore the unwritten institutional violence of migration policies. The premise of the research is designed to inquire about the “*How*” and the “*Why*” a sovereign constitutes legislation resulting in Necropolitical foundations. The methodology chapter further describes the roadmap of the research and the sourcing process.

¹ Survival Migration, 2013

² Refuge beyond Reach, 2019

³ The Refugee in International Society between Sovereigns, 2008

⁴ Violent Inaction, 2017

The empirical chapter, the Oracle and the Odyssey, incorporates the findings on policy analysis and ethnographic research into a narrative that describes how the U.S. created the conditions for the necropolitical frameworks to take effect, and how this framework was operationalized during the Afghan migration crisis. The findings daringly suggest that the U.S. facilitated the migration to occur by deliberately mutilating the sovereignty of the Afghan government, and hampering the prospect of the formation of a unitary and recognized Afghan sovereign after the U.S.'s withdrawal. The U.S. had further divided the population through its Special Immigration Visa program (SIV), which built a separate identity narrative for the group Afghans, whose de facto sovereign protectorate would be the U.S. government.

The policy analysis then suggests the U.S. government deliberately created a labyrinthic network of bureaucratic entrapment, which prolonged the migration process for the SIV applicants. This temporal dimension was complemented by the U.S.'s utilization of remote migration policies and caging, which spatially confined the migrants to the U.S. government's sheer escapades. Despite the horrendous situation the migrants described during the caging period, the policies enacted by the policymakers are interpreted to deliberately produce minimal improvements, preserve the status quo, and make use of the involuntary labor of the migrants – a necropeonage. Most grotesque, the study found how U.S. policymakers would essentially use policy introduction as a method to capitalize on the misery of the migrants in promoting their electoral base, thereby acting under domestic mechanisms of sovereign consolidation.

Examining the settlement policies and the use of caging yielded the most concentrated results on how the migration policies for refugees consolidate the U.S.'s sovereignty both externally and internally. Externally, sovereignty is consolidated through the militarization of the migration process. The third-country that hosts the refugees before their departure to the U.S., acts as U.S.'s buffer – the external dumping ground for unwanted refugees. The militarized nature of the evacuations reconstructs the image of the U.S. military from an invader to a savior – contributing to the axiom that necessitates the presence of the U.S. military beyond its sovereign territories. Internally, the caging of the migrants serves two means of consolidating the government's sovereignty within the U.S.: Firstly, policies regarding the caging are framed around American security and protecting Americans against “others”. By caging “others” the sovereign enjoys the domestic support on the impression that it is fulfilling its responsibility of protecting and homogenizing the subjects against the “others”. Secondly, cages are used as spaces to re-educate the migrants and introduce them to the American way of life. This is interpreted as indoctrinating them to the way of being an expectedly homogenized subject of the sovereign.

Through this research and posing the central question “cui bono?” we explore the avenues through which the necropolitical frameworks are operationalized to serve the interest of the sovereign – even under a humanitarian facade. The extrication of the clandestine violence of migration from migration policies embraces future policy analysts and relevant scholars to look beyond the numbers and positivist presuppositions. The utilization of a necropolitical framework, although daunting, is a requisite to scrutinizing the violent institution of migration policies, which has left a gap in academia.

2. Necropolitical Discourse

The concept at the crux of this research, leveraging the liveability of individuals, coalesces with Foucault's principle of Biopolitics – sets of mechanisms through which human lives and processes are controlled by dominant actors, the state(s), through the enactment of power. This concept was further explored in the context of colonialism by Mbembe, who dubbed the practice of deciding over an individual's life, as Necropolitics – “the capacity to define who matters and who does not, who is disposable and who is not.”⁵

Necropolitics illuminates how different humans are assigned quantifiable values which differentiate the level of importance and attention they can receive from the states. Yet, the calculus of liveability is an incredibly complex subject with a myriad of axes, varying for different sovereigns with their own prioritized subjects. In an oblique conceptualization, the further an individual is situated from the ends of the axes, the more precarious their life is estimated through Necropolitics. The sovereign in this pretext, could be the body or the agency which holds “the right to kill”⁶, Mbembe says, through active violence, or, as I argue, the inaction to deter violence.

Mbembe cites the words of Foucault, on “the sovereign right to kill (Droit de glaive) and the mechanisms of biopower”⁷ as a constitutive element of every modern state. Foucault interprets the Nazi regime as the most sophisticated case of exercising the right to kill – wherein the government had cultivated the essential social structures and infrastructures in a formidable consolidation of their final solution.⁸ In parallel, creating a fallible infrastructure, with strong dependencies on an exogenous sovereign, with a limited capacity of circumvention from the structure in case of failure, is what I interpret as necropolitical conditions for the subjects within this structure

The condition Afghanistan was left with, rendered a segment of the population as dependent subjects of the U.S. In terms, Afghans were left with a fallible defense and economic infrastructure, with a limited capacity for circumvention – given the natural geography of the country and its distrusting relations with its neighboring countries. In Mbembe's terms, this is the death-world– “new and unique forms of social existence in which vast populations are subjected to conditions of life conferring upon them the status of living dead.”⁹ In the death-world laws are suspended to exert pure control through biopower – or Necropower in the context of this research.

⁵ Achille Mbembe and Steven Corcoran, *Necropolitics* (Durham and London: Duke University Press, 2019). p.80

⁶ Ibid. p.60

⁷ Ibid. p.71

⁸ Ibid. p.67

⁹ Ibid. p.92

In Foucauldian terms, to live at the mercy of a sovereign state is to be bare-life, ripe for extermination or escapades of the states. This unchecked principle could be detrimental to not only the migrants but also to the democratic context: Vulnerable social groups live in sheer obedience and compliance from the fear of the sovereign state's retaliatory response for demanding democratic reforms. This unionizing fear, as Braidotti recognizes, stems from 'death' – the “inhuman inside all of us [...] an all too human quality that binds us”¹⁰, when confronted with the physical extinction of the body and conscious of one's terminal finitude.

¹⁰ Annette-Carina van der Zaag, “On Posthuman Subjectivity,” *Journal of Cultural Economy* 9, no. 3 (2015): pp. 330-336, <https://doi.org/10.1080/17530350.2015.1040436>. p.334

2.1 The Migrant

The inadequacy of the refugee regime in defining the conditions of a refugee has been a subject of scrutiny by a myriad of scholars from different schools of International Relations. In 1951, the convention relating to the status of refugees assembled to establish a reciprocal obligation for all sovereigns to not forcibly return refugees present on their territory, and provide essential provisions to the refugees would be entitled to.

Within the confines of a territory dominated by a malevolent sovereign, the only available means to acquire protection and dignified respect for human rights, maybe to leave the country.¹¹ By the virtue of vaguely defined categories for refugees, many individuals fleeing failed states are often denied protection, as their status does not fall within the definitions of refugees.¹² Who is entitled to refugee protection?

2.2.1 Outdated Regime

This inadequacy was also noted by immigration scholar, Alexander Betts, who argued the 1951 convention was a product of its time – the cold war. The author cites the original intent of the convention was to provide asylum to individuals who were the targets of persecution by the states and by non-state actors – whence the state would turn a blind eye to the plausibility of violence against the individuals. With the decline of authoritarian regimes following the end of the Cold War, the trend of seeking asylum from repressive and authoritarian states reared for a gradual decline. As Betts argues, “This trend means that fewer people are fleeing persecution resulting from the acts of states while more are fleeing human rights deprivations resulting from the omissions of weak states that are unable or unwilling to ensure fundamental rights.”¹³

The now-outdated refuge regime was primarily designed as the consequences of the holocaust, the circumstances of civil treatment of displaced individuals in postwar Europe.¹⁴ The regime defined a refugee as a person who “owing to a well-founded fear of being persecuted for reasons of race, religion, nationality, membership of a particular social group or political opinion, is outside the country of his nationality and is unable or, owing to such fear unwilling to avail himself of the protection of that country.”¹⁵

¹¹ Alexander Betts, *Survival Migration: Failed Governance and the Crisis of Displacement* (Ithaca: Cornell University Press, 2013). p.17

¹² Ibid. p.2

¹³ Ibid. p.2

¹⁴ Ibid. p.13

¹⁵ Ibid.

Whereas the convention by de jure secures the protection of individuals under targeted persecution, its loose structure and inconsistencies undermine its humanitarian ethos. Refugees who don't fall within the definition of the convention, are not only left unprotected, but also possibly “more likely to be rounded up, detained, and deported.”¹⁶

2.2.2 State Fragilities

When the fundamental needs of the population within the confines of territory are not met by the sovereign due to failing institutions, judicial collapse, and weak governance, domestic remedies may be unavailable to give provisional support to the basic survival needs of the populace. States such as Libya, Yemen, South Sudan, and Afghanistan with an abysmal record of human rights abuse are the most vivid testament to the casual relations between the fragility of the state and outbound migration of the able population.

Betts associates weak governance and state fragility as the most dominant driver of modern migration. Weak states, as Betts argues, “are unable or unwilling to ensure even the most fundamental rights, wider sets of threats may lead to very severe levels of rights deprivation that simply cannot be met without—as a last resort—leaving the country.”¹⁷

In parallel with Betts' interpretation, Afghans who chose to leave the country –if not specifically subjected to targeted persecution– could fall between the gaps between refugees and voluntary migrants. “Externally displaced people, [...] people in distress, [...] distress migration, [...] and vulnerable irregular migrants”¹⁸ are among the labels Betts cites that have been used by scholars to fill the gap between the dichotomy of Refugee and Voluntary migrants. There is a unifying need among scholars to provide a more expansive and inclusive concept for refugees. Yet, as with both Betts and myself, there is an easy lack of consensus on how to “conceptualize those people who cross international borders who have a human rights-based entitlement not to be forcibly returned to their country of origin.”¹⁹

To this end, Betts posits the term *Survival Migration* to describe a phenomenon where a person is unable to access fundamental rights in the country of origin, and is hence coerced to seek those rights in another country.²⁰ Although befitting to the context of the Afghans' and the frenzy to escape the country following the Taliban takeover, certain conditions used by Betts to build conceptual clarity essentially limit the relevance of the term to the crux of this research. However given the matter of

¹⁶ Ibid.

¹⁷ Ibid. p.20

¹⁸ Ibid. p.23

¹⁹ Ibid.

²⁰ Ibid.

survival and the existentialist approach, Survival Migration embodies an adequate starting point to develop a concept within academic conventions to appropriately encompass the agential elements and individuals subjected to this research.

2.2.2 Survival Migration

Betts defines survival migrants as “persons who are outside their country of origin because of an existential threat for which they have no access to a domestic remedy or resolution.”²¹ To fill the analytical gap and encompass the totality of individuals who are within the limbo of falling outside the international refugee law, while having an entitlement to not be returned to their country of origin under International Human Right law²², Betts defines three conditions to narrow the concept of who is a survival migrant:

1. They’re situated outside the country of origin and have access to the international community, and the international community has access to them²³
2. They’re threatened by an existential threat – not to the maximal extent of the right to life, but also core elements of human dignity²⁴
3. They’re unable to find a solution domestically due to the fragile status of the state, and crossing the border is their only viable solution²⁵

Of the three elements introduced by Betts, the first is sufficient to cross it from relevancy to the subjects of this research. Many Afghans who fall under the second condition, are still situated within Afghanistan, being subjected to the Necropolitics and necropolicies of the Taliban government. Given the inaccessibility of the international community to this category of Afghans, they would not be considered either Migrant or survival migrants. Yet, given a sizeable number of them, particularly the collaborators with the U.S. and the allies, could’ve expected to be evacuated due to their vulnerable domestic status, it wouldn’t be outlandish to recognize them within conditions of “Survival Migrants”. The existential threat and inability to find domestic solutions, reduce the liveability of this category of Afghans to be coerced to either move outside the territories of Afghanistan, or be moved from the territories of Afghanistan.

This conceptualization of Afghan migrants is in fact closely within the framework posited by Betts, as individuals who “have a human rights-based entitlement not to be returned to their country of origin” for their means of liveability. Yet, the concept of the International Community is pivotal to the space

²¹ Ibid. p.24

²² Ibid. p.25

²³ Ibid.

²⁴ Ibid.

²⁵ Ibid.

provided by Betts, and it is dependent on the role of how sovereign states behave with one another and their subjects to maintain the global order. Hence, for a survival migrant to be within the security framework of the international community, they must be cross-border displaced.

The international community, in this sense, is the sovereign host, which still posits the capacity to exercise necropower by choosing to send the migrants back to their country of origin. In this spirit, then how must we define an Afghan who collaborated with the U.S. forces, and now needs an external sovereign's protection for survival means, while being yet within the sovereign territory of the Taliban? Is this subject not a survivalist? Who is this subject's sovereign – the Afghan government? The international community-at-large? If being a survival migrant requires transitioning the capacity of liveability from one sovereign to another, is this other sovereign purely confined to territories beyond the reach of the original sovereign?

Although “Survival Migration” in its own right –the English school of International Relations- is an all-encompassing terminology that aptly covers the analytical gap needed to define the category of migrants between volunteering migrants and refugees, it falls short in filling another void within this phenomenon of *evacuation/rescue* migration: Agents who are ought to migrate through an external sovereign's behest.

2.2.3 *Necropeon*

The codependent relation between the sovereign and the migrant subject is explored in-depth in the next chapters. Yet, given the lack of temporal clarity on the ontological relation of an Afghan migrant with its sovereign, there is a need to conceptualize this phenomenon before establishing relevant operationalizations.

The Afghans who fall within the Survival Migrant category, consider themselves to be “Panahjoo”, which translates to “Safety-seeker” or “Asylum seeker”. Yet, seeking asylum domestically is void due to state fragility, and if the subject is not outside the sovereign territory, they're merely considered internally displaced. As the following chapters will further explore, an Afghan in such precarious limbo is simultaneously subjected to two sovereigns with necropower which withhold the right of bare-life:

- 1 - The Taliban government to “let them live” until they leave
- 2 - The U.S. government to “not let them die” until they leave

Despite the U.S. government maintaining no sovereign control over the territories of Afghanistan, it is externalized borders that protect those within the framework of evacuation, do subject collaborating

Afghans and an ambiguously broader circle to sovereign protection. To properly categorize this particular set of bi-sovereign Afghans with existential dependence, I posit to use the neologism of Necropeon. The reluctance to refer to the subjects as mere migrants stems from the impression that the “Migrant” connotation is devoid of laboring the individual for their survival means. Chapter 2.4.7 Necropeonage is dedicated to expanding on the choice of this neologism.

2.2 The Sovereign

The previous chapter discussed the importance of sovereignty in determining the identity of the migrants in the framework of the English School of International Relations. Consequently, further exploration of this perplexing concept maintains consistent adherence to this theoretical framework. By determining *who* and *what* is the sovereign, we identify the agents and institutions that reserved the capacity to exercise Necropower. This identification of the Sovereign will further enable this research's capacity to examine the operationalization framework of Necropolitics. In this section, we will explore: Is it truly possible that an Afghan could be simultaneously subjected to two separate sovereigns? What makes and legitimizes a sovereign? Is a sovereign's reach to its subjects bound to the territorial boundaries?

2.3.1 English School International Relations

The English school interprets the international system to be uniform and static with each sovereign having the reciprocal responsibilities of adhering to certain universal principles. This axiom, to Emma Haddad, is overestimated and debatable. She believes sovereigns in International Relations posits a more dynamic and fluid system with plenty of blurred lines, even within the constituted territorial system.²⁶ This understanding is further challenged by the role of the refugee, as an anomaly, for the phenomenon that the refugee can cross the territorial systems, challenge the static concept of sovereignty, and citizenship as a natural pre-given feature.²⁷

While the English school interprets legal order based on the coexistence of sovereigns, the role of independent actors is also accounted for – enabling grounds to assess the sovereign and subject relations with greater scrutiny. The refugee's position vis-a`-vis individual states has been studied by Haddad to a great extent to narrate the dynamics of the sovereignty and provide a critical understanding of the “contradictions states face in both understanding the refugee as a concept and offering protection to the refugee as an individual.”²⁸

By studying the response of an external sovereign to migration phenomena, Haddad accentuates the relationship between the sovereign and the migrating subjects' country of origin. In this sense, referencing Haddad's assessment of sovereign relations with one another and the migrants indulges us in better understanding the relationship between Afghan necropeon and the Taliban state, Afghan necropeons and the U.S. government, and the sovereign recognition between the Taliban state and the U.S. government.

²⁶ Emma Haddad, *The Refugee in International Society between Sovereigns* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2008). p.11

²⁷ Ibid. p.14

²⁸ Ibid. p.11

2.3.2 Territorial Sovereignty

The birth of a sovereign within the confines of a territory is consolidated through the construction of a single sovereign government, to which the population of the territory owes their final allegiance to.²⁹ Thus, the Taliban takeover of Afghanistan and the capitulation of the previous regime established the Islamic Emirate of Afghanistan as the de facto sovereign of the Afghan people, whether or not they were protected by any external sovereign through the previous government. Those who lack fidelity and allegiance to the state, are as much under the necropower of the sovereign as those who have fulfilled their oath of allegiance.

Consolidation over a sovereign dominion entails the duty to “represent and protect all those who fall within the sovereign jurisdiction of the state: a failure of the sovereign to fulfill these duties has the potential to produce refugees.”³⁰ Thus, sovereignty also carries the responsibility to ensure the well-being of all citizens, with respect to their human rights. Reiterating Betts’ argument from the previous section, then the failure to provide a system of substantive sovereignty to protect the fundamental needs of the subjects results in the subjects seeking protection from an external sovereignty – an evident case with Afghanistan.

To answer what creates a migrant and the migration phenomena, Haddad traces the migration movements to the failing reciprocal relations between the sovereign and subjects. She posits, that when the relationships between the two fail, the subjects are coerced to leave the country. Yet, as the result of failing relations with the sovereign, and the sovereign’s relation with the international community of sovereigns, nothing externally guarantees the acceptance of the migrant by an external sovereign.³¹ The exception to this, as the previous chapter discussed, is if the migrant falls within the limited framework of “Refugee” based on the 1951 convention. In the same frame, if an individual within the state makes all criteria of categorization as a “refugee” but yet hasn’t left the country, then, this individual is merely the “internally displaced person”, which remains an internal issue for her state of origin.³² The chapter 4, the Oracle and the Odyssey explores the limitations of this principle for the Afghans within Afghanistan who were granted protection by the U.S. through the latter’s special migration policies.

This defining condition, to leave the territories, was also embedded in Betts’ Survival Migrant typology under the pretense that the access of the international society to the individual is necessary to extricate the subject from the necropower of its sovereign. An Afghan who hasn’t been able to leave the country is not ought to accept the support of the international society, as they still lay within the

²⁹ Ibid.

³⁰ Ibid. p.85

³¹ Ibid. p.60

³² Ibid. p.61

sovereignty of the Taliban Afghanistan – where the state maintains a monopoly of necropower over the necropeon. For the necropeon, the escape from necropower doesn't end with leaving the territories of their malevolent sovereign. Upon leaving the territories of one sovereign, the subject has entered the territories of another sovereign within the international society. The power to deny settlement, or restrict liveability to bare-life, extends the necropower of one sovereign to the other. Arguably, the necropower over the migrant isn't intrinsic to the sovereigns but is rather transmitted through the movements of the necropeon in a metaphorical fornication of insects around a sugar cube.

2.3.3 *International Society*

From the prism of international society, the global order is divided into sovereign states, wherein the sovereigns have authority over internal control and external autonomy.³³ Haddad compares sovereign states to Janus-faced figures, which simultaneously maintain an inward gaze towards their domestic subjects while keeping an outward contact with the other states. The combination of this inward and outward look is what grants the sovereign its expected authority. A sovereign entity is considered a sovereign if it is treated as a sovereign by other sovereign states.³⁴ This principle, as Haddad points out, demands outward equal and reciprocal recognition from other members of the international society, and “that a sovereign state must refrain from interfering in the domestic affairs of other sovereigns, and that territory will be the ultimate object of political life.”³⁵

Haddad further argues how the causal relations between negative and positive sovereignty could allude to the creation of refugees. In the changing nature of sovereignty, Bolt describes Positive Sovereignty as an attribute of a government “which has the capacity to provide political goods for those it claims to represent”³⁶, where a government is essentially its own master. Conversely, negative sovereignty is where a government is void of external interference, while lacking the capacity to provide rudimentary fundamental needs for its subjects.³⁷

The international society's fundamental assumption is that states “possess positive sovereignty and are therefore good for their citizens, yet these obligations are far from always met.”³⁸ However, when a gap is cleaved between negative sovereignty of the states in the international society and positive sovereignty of the individual states, or vice versa, the discrepancy results in the creation of refugees.³⁹

³³ Ibid. p.48

³⁴ Ibid.

³⁵ Ibid.

³⁶ Michael Bolt, “The Changing Nature of Sovereignty,” *E-International Relations*, 2013, <https://doi.org/https://www.e-ir.info/2013/10/17/the-changing-nature-of-sovereignty/>.

³⁷ Ibid.

³⁸ Ibid. p.4

³⁹ Ibid.

The case of Afghanistan in either argument stands to be a global anomaly that undermines much of our conventional understanding of sovereigns. While the Taliban government has been on a charming offensive to establish itself internationally, it has achieved minimal *de facto* success. Although government representatives join diplomatic missions with Ankara and Doha in foreign missions, the state lacks *de jure* recognition. Even before the state capitulation in 2001, only Pakistan, Saudi Arabia and the United Arab Emirates recognized the regime's sovereignty.

In this virtue, it is rather easy to explain how the Afghan migrants situated within Afghanistan seek protection from an external sovereign. Not only the Taliban regime's failure to provide fundamental needs of its subject is a glorified example of negative sovereignty, it devoids the Afghans from the capacity of recognized statehood beyond the territories of Afghanistan. Even without considering how the Afghan government has failed domestically, the matter of lacking sovereign recognition internationally sets the country tantamount to prison for its inhabitants with maximal restriction of cross-border movement.

Haddad further traces the creation of refugees to the failures of the international society, by arguing in a sovereign's effort to homogenize its territorial space, some subjects are inevitably forcibly moved between borders and sovereigns – wherein the state's need to homogenize in the first place, was a measure to deter the international society's domestic interference. States, then retain the right “to decide who may enter their territory and hence whom they will protect.”⁴⁰ While this is a relevant argument to describe the Afghan exodus, Haddad's daring assertion is fatalistic and lacks clarity and relevance even in the British school's interpretation of sovereignty. Migration and movement have been a human phenomenon even prior to the creation of the first sovereign territories. The attributes Haddad yields as Sovereign behavior –to homogenize and control– are essentially intrinsic human behaviors.

⁴⁰ Ibid. p.69

2.3 The Bureaucracy

The two previous chapters emphasized the importance of a migrant's access to the international society as the first rite of passage. Yet, the trails to access the international society are far more convoluted than merely crossing the border. A byzantine conundrum of legal pathways and confusingly opaque humanitarian corridors greatly complicate the movements of the prospecting migrants. The devastating results of this are vivid in the horrific video of Afghans clutching the landing gear of U.S. Airforce C-17 during its takeoff, just to fall to their demise. In the event of such an incident, the international society must contemplate *how* and *why* this was deemed preferred to a legal migration? What drives Afghans to seek refuge on an active airport's tarmac?

David S.Fitzgerald's "Refuge Beyond Reach" provides an excellent insight into the precarious passways Liberal Democracies have created in an effort to repel migrants. Fitzgerald begins his book with the drowning of Alan Kurdi, the two years old Kurdish boy who was washed up to the Turkish shores, after the rubber lifeboat of migrant smugglers was drowned. In an investigation of what constitutes the creation of similar irregular migration passages, Fitzgerald explores myriads of bureaucratic, humanitarian, and security entrapment, designed to deter migration – at least through legal means.

Studying the work of Fitzgerald gives readers the fundamental precursors to understanding how policies are operationalized. Within this frame of operationalization, we may debate whether the execution of Necropower is an unpremeditated byproduct of the entrapment policies or a deliberate necropolitical technology of controlling the individuals.

2.4.1 Remote Control

The first legal barriers for the Afghab migrants to access International Society are the remote control policies imposed by the U.S. These policies entail the U.S. government to extend its authority beyond its territorial boundaries "in extensive, routine collaboration to track and deter [migrants] and particular groups trying to cross borders."⁴¹ Fitzgerald further argues this system of territorialized asylum is primarily designed to keep away undesired Asylum Seekers by confining them to third "safe" countries in externalized territories.⁴²

Remote control policies are at the crux of operationalizing Necropolitics within migration policies. Although Fitzgerald provides an extensive list of remote control policies adopted by the governments

⁴¹ David Fitzgerald, *Refuge beyond Reach: How Rich Democracies Repel Asylum Seekers* (New York, NY: Oxford University Press, 2019). p.12

⁴² Ibid.

of the Global North, I will primarily focus on tools of Externalizing borders, Caging, and the Hippocratic bubble – as the case is most relevant to the Afghan migration.

2.4.2 Externalizing Borders

Externalizing borders entails to intercepting the entry of the migrant to the host country, and the migrant's departure from the country of origin. For instance, by not recognizing the passports issued by the Taliban government, the regimes that do not recognize the sovereignty of the Taliban, have engaged in an extreme form of externalized borders, where the departure of Afghans is denied through any dignified legal avenue. Survival migrants are coerced to cross borders without any possible legal pathway. Fitzgerald applies the same practice to the U.S. Coast Guard when they intercept the people on boats sailing from the Caribbean islands. By controlling and intercepting the refugee boats coming from the Haiti and Cuba, the U.S. has inadvertently made cages out of the island countries.⁴³

By manipulating territoriality, governments establish sovereign territories outside their country, where the function of borders is extended “hundreds or even thousands of kilometers beyond the state’s territory”⁴⁴ Externalizing borders circumvents holding the governments accountable to the international asylum regime – enforced by the international society. As Fitzgerald points out, by placing the migrants in a third safe country or an extra-territorial destination, the host country is able to deport the migrants back to the country of origin, without violating non-refoulement – the law which forbids returning asylum seekers to a country where they’d be endangered.⁴⁵ The remote policies then grant an absolute position of necropower, where the receiving country holds the right to return the migrants. In extension, this corresponds to the right to the right to let them live, or leave them to die.

2.4.3 Panopticon Camps

Another form of externalizing the borders is where the government designs fortifications at the entrance to their territory. A classic example of this would be the Ellice Islands, which later became the foundation rock under the statue of Lady Liberty. Although this may have a positive connotation of “Hope” and the “Home before Home” in the the government’s narration, the special rules that apply to these areas are more in parallel with archaic medieval barricades built outside the castles. Fitzgerald points to these barricades as means of creating the “fiction that asylum seekers are not physically present in the state’s territory, or at least not fully within its walls, where they would have greater rights like access to lawyers and independent review of their appeals”⁴⁶

⁴³ Ibid. p.9

⁴⁴ Ibid. p.171

⁴⁵ Ibid.

⁴⁶ Ibid. p.9

This method is also accompanied by Caging, which keeps the refugees in an enclosed area either within their country of origin, in a third-country, or in the receiving country. In either case, the confinement of refugees within cages bars their access to international society. If the cages are located in the country of origin, then the migrants are merely internally displaced people – another fallacy that restricted this research from using Survival Migrant label proposed by Betts.

International Organization for Migration (IOM) has been notoriously criticized for enabling caging, by receiving funds from the Global North to “fund refugee camps and centers for asylum seekers, usually in countries neighboring conflict zones, and to repatriate refugees who are willing or can be made to return home”⁴⁷ By enabling bare-life, and provision of the most basic and fundamental needs for asylum seekers, IOM camps are hardly differentiated from a Panopticon prison architecture: they provide food, shelter, logistics, and mass surveillance – primarily to prevent further movement of the refugees towards the global North.⁴⁸ This practice is oddly in parallel with Mbembe’s original proposition on Necropolitics: To keep the subjects alive, but not living.

2.4.4 Hippocratic Bubble and Civil Society

By referencing the works of psychologists, Fitzgerald posits that “people are more likely to mobilize around saving the lives of identifiable individuals in close proximity”, and thus remote control policies are deliberately created to thwart this humanitarian impulse.⁴⁹ This peculiar practice of necropolitics is however seemingly entrenched even within the U.S.’s domestic policies. Fitzgerald references the work of Sociologist, Alejandro Portes, who describes “U.S. hospitals often deliberately create obstacles between sick people seeking health care and the doctors who have taken the Hippocratic Oath to render aid”⁵⁰ to institutionally restrict the access of patients without sufficient resources and insurance to receive medical attention. In a literal close proximation to the case with remote policies, patients must pass “hospital’s clerical gatekeepers and physical barriers surrounding the examination room” before they reach the space the doctors Hippocratic is constituted.⁵¹

A major deterrence to Fitzgerald’s Hippocratic Bubble is the role of domestic and international civil societies. According to the author, advocacy of civil societies, combined with legal action built up over the last decades have won more victories for the Asylum seekers in the courts, than the policymakers in the congress⁵² Where the governments use externalized borders and cages to deter migrants, they must engage in policies that do not enforce any ruthless and harsh treatment for the migrants. Else, the

⁴⁷ Ibid. p.40

⁴⁸ Ibid.

⁴⁹ Ibid. p.253

⁵⁰ Ibid. p.254

⁵¹ Ibid. p.254

⁵² Ibid. 255

segment of civil society responsible for investigating and publicizing these policies will trigger a domino effect for other segments of civil society to engage in protesting and delegitimizing the government.⁵³ An infamous case of this exact incident is how the Australian government was scrutinized for using the Christmas island as a detention camp for the unwanted migrants — leading to the camp’s temporary closure in 2018.

2.4.6 Legal Accountability

Through either caging or hyper-externalizing borders, governments in the global north evade refugee protection laws. Despite what Fitzgerald dubs as a “Hyper-legal” logic of policies, many asylum seekers have managed to bypass every deadly barrier to reach sanctuaries one way or another.⁵⁴ From then on, the refugees are not yet guaranteed protection, as they must still carry the thirteenth labor of Hercules: the Bureaucratic Entrapment. The shortcomings of the English school of International Relations could be explored from the prism of American Realism, as the subsequent sections intend to follow. By accounting for how American realism rationalizes the decisions of policymakers, we’ll develop an analytical understanding of how deliberate bureaucratic entrapment serve the government.

Fitzgerald's explores the phenomena of legal entrapment by first exploring how migration policies are created within different International Relations schools. By the virtue of the embedded liberalism in the global north, the government's avoid adopting restrictive policies that could restrain the market economies.⁵⁵ Liberal policymakers, thus, primarily focus on generation of demand for trade, tourism, and Labour migration drives the economy. Through this prioritization, the most punitive policies on migration are tossed from one end of the table to the realist’s side.

In the realist theoretical frame, the states primarily act in their own interest and prioritize security, by dismissing the “relevance of international human rights law such as the refugee regime.”⁵⁶ However, beyond apathy for humanitarian interest and benevolence of the policymakers, the realists also have an interest in drafting incentivizing migration policies – which coincide with stronger domestic security and unity. The work of Haddad, although based on the English School, examined the relationship between a sovereign and a migrant, and how the latter’s provision of the “Otherness” gives domestic validity and recognition to the sovereign – homogenizing the subjects. Haddad describes the phenomena of human displacement as a needed side-effect of state-building, where it provided a distinction between insiders and outsiders, “to consolidate the concept of citizenship and the sovereign role of the state.”⁵⁷ Haddad adds, “people need ‘others’ to be able to invent for themselves a ‘we’ as

⁵³ Ibid.

⁵⁴ Ibid. 253

⁵⁵ Ibid. 65

⁵⁶ Ibid. 50

⁵⁷ Haddad, p.55

distinct from a ‘they’.”⁵⁸ To this end, per the American realism, we may argue, Realist policymakers also have a beef to pick from the carcass of Necropolitical policies – where the sovereign rule is strengthened through the perils of migration, the advent of the “Others”. Even per Morgenthau’s classical realism, the survival of the sovereign state within an anarchic international system is dependent on the anarchist/migrants.

Ergo, by constructing policies that seemingly restrain legal migration and create illegal corridors for irregular migrants, the realist policymaker achieves two milestones: Restricts total migration of the “others”, and strengthens the government sovereignty for domestic subjects, who rely on the former to prevent illegal migration.

2.4.7 Necropeonage

Through a closer inspection of the works of Alexander Whyte, we may also entertain the idea of Necropeon being far more appealing to the neoliberal and neorealist institutionalists who share “similar methodology, epistemology, and ontology. The methods by which neorealists and neoliberals study the world are analogous”⁵⁹ with them being “complementary as opposed competitive approaches to International Relations.”⁶⁰ The compatible synthesis of the two is additionally strengthened by their similar position on the international system as a whole, where the states are the main rational actors, shaped by means of gaining advantages from the global anarchy.⁶¹

The suffix of Necro– for the neologism of Necropeon is used to emphasize the practice of Peonage within the framework of Necropolitics. Peonage is defined by Webster's dictionary as “the use of laborers bound in servitude because of debt.” A survival migrant, an irregular migrant, or an asylum seeker, are bound to follow limited corridors of liveability to avoid deportation to their country of origin. The owed debt in this context is the life of the peon; the peonage is what they do to be let lived or to be not left to die. Any labour served by the migrants –through existing as a survival migrant– is involuntary, and any means of producing tangible outcomes from it is necropeonage.

In theory, the impression that an irregular migrant’s arrival to a host country serves to strengthen the government’s sovereignty –particularly if the migrant has used illegal corridors– creates an incentive to maintain the illegal status of the migrant, and create deliberately defective policies for future migrants bypass legal migration.

⁵⁸ Ibid.

⁵⁹ Alexander Whyte, “Neorealism and Neoliberal Institutionalism: Born of the Same Approach?,” *E-International Relations*, 2012, <https://doi.org/ISSN: ISSN 2053-8626>. p.3

⁶⁰ Ibid.

⁶¹ Ibid. p.6

If an Afghan migrant is willing to climb the landing gears of C-17 during a takeoff, it's not improbable for a "Neo-neo thinker" to consider what else would he have done. With this thought, the practice of (necro)peonage, is any utility of the peon's condition – a line in policy whitepapers written in invisible ink. The next following section operationalizes the neologism of Necropeon and Necropeonage, with reference to the studies of Davies, whose research is the foundation-stone of mine as the first empirical research on the operationalization of Necropolitics in refugee migration policies.

2.4 Kabul in Calais

In the study of conditions of forced migrants in Calais, Davies refers to Mbembe's principle of 'permanent injury' in arguing:

“The permanent wounding of individuals, rather than their direct and active killing, can be used as a means of control. Suffering therefore can become a political technology, where certain groups are exposed to conditions in which they are “kept alive but in a state of injury”⁶²

Mbembe further introduces “permanent injury”, as a bolstering retainer of Necropolitics. It implies constraining one from the opportunity of changing one's execrable and hazardous state of being, without assistance or the aid of the overpowering sovereign. Davies emphasizes that “when such securities are removed, regulated to exclude marginalized groups or kept purposely insufficient”(Ibid. 1269), individuals are deliberately sanctioned with “letting [them] die.”⁶³

In Davies' research, the migrants are constrained by the EU law which dictates they can seek asylum in only the first European country they've arrived in. If the initial asylum application is rejected, they can re-apply after a year without even being able to request another EU state's subsistence support. Being under coerced mobility towards another EU state, the migrants must rely on their own for their means of survival, which often pertains to illegal labour. Davies recognizes this scheme as a “hyper-precarious situation of bureaucratic entrapment”⁶⁴, where migrants are denied provision in the only state they can apply for asylum while being coerced to move to another state with illegibility to receive any means of sustenance.⁶⁵

By accounting for the works of Fitzgerald and Haddad, we can trace how this hyper-precarious bureaucratic trap could be deliberately created to indirectly serve policies and functions pertaining to Necropolitics. Whereas the Davies' work is primarily an ethnography of how migrants voyage through this legal conundrum, my research will focus on attempts to untangle the Byzantium. The next chapter on methodology outlines strategies used for policy analysis, and the strategies adopted from the works of Davies. Thus, this section of the literature review also serves as a prelude to the methodology chapter.

⁶² Thom Davies, Arshad Isakjee, and Surindar Dhesi, “Violent Inaction: The Necropolitical Experience of Refugees in Europe,” *Antipode* 49, no. 5 (2017): pp. 1263-1284, <https://doi.org/10.1111/anti.12325>, p.1268

⁶³ Ibid.

⁶⁴ Ibid. 1273

⁶⁵ Ibid.

2.5.1 Defining Necropolitics

Davies writes, that while Mbembe introduces necropolitics in relation to the brutal oppression found in colonial spaces, the concept is not antithetical to Foucault's biopolitics. Whereas the Biopolitical framework is an emphasis on *actions* for allocation of resources for the management of life, Necropolitical framework focuses on the instances where *inaction* holds precedent. The *inaction* on saving a life is fatalistically in-correspondence to *action* on not saving a life. Thus, biopolitical and necropolitical are intrinsically linked, and the “the prefix of necro- may apply outside outright death”⁶⁶ In the same virtue, biopolitical technologies, such as fingerprints and identification are used to provide legal avenues of protection for the migrants, are also Necropolitical technologies which could deliberately hamper the avenues.⁶⁷ Through citing Foucault, Davies further adds that forced fingerprinting and biometric identification used by Italian authorities is further seen as a technique for subjugating bodies in order to control populations.⁶⁸

Colonial spaces of Mbembe’s Necropolitical are further compared with the spaces created for migrants in Calais and across southern Europe. The camps, or cages, according to Fitzgerald, provide space for slow violence as delayed destruction. While the individuals confined to the cages are not killed, they’re allowed to “suffer the brutal indignity of harmful spatial environments”.⁶⁹ Davies warns against drawing a stark divide between such structural violence and direct violence. While the latter is rarely legitimized, the author hints to the structural violence as a byproduct of social order itself.⁷⁰

2.5.2 Bureaucratic Bind

Davies further divides political measures as actions and inaction to examine where forms of violence are inflicted through migration policies, by withholding the means to live.⁷¹ Davies' research is an excellent ethnographic work on the Odyssey migrants have to go through to find bare liveability within the EU migration policies. This research is however limited in the sense of not accounting for the full prism of sovereign and subject relations. Based on the aforementioned works of Haddad, Fitzgerald and Betts, we can argue the Odyssey experienced by the migrants begins far before their arrival at the EU borders. It begins in Libya and Algeria where the smugglers use fragile lifeboats to voyage across the Mediterranean before they’re intercepted by the Italian marines. To provide a grander spectrum of this Odyssey, my work will additionally also expand on the necropolitics exercised by a sovereign’s hyper-externalized territories.

⁶⁶ Ibid.

⁶⁷ Ibid. p.1268

⁶⁸ Ibid. p.1272

⁶⁹ Ibid. p.1270

⁷⁰ Ibid.

⁷¹ Ibid.

The de jure process a refugee is dared to set forth, binds the refugees to process their biometric registration, before they can expect to be housed across different Italian regions. The EU laws, however, similar to that of the U.S., don't shy from constructing the Hippocratic Bubble. Davies reports that the Asylum seekers experience a strikingly different venue than what's been legally set for them by the EU policymakers. Davies reports, "[migrants] routinely indicated that upon arrival in Italy, they were denied provision and shelter, often only being allowed to spend a maximum of 2–5 days in emergency reception centers before being made to leave"⁷²

Dejected from expecting dignified treatment and accommodation within the formal legal framework, Davies's participants described "having to find spaces to sleep under entrances of commercial properties, in public parks (from which they would be forcefully removed) and in train stations"⁷³ In reference to chapter 2.4.6 Legal Accountability and 2.4.7 Necropeonage, this phenomena provides an opportunity to assess how the policymakers or the sovereign benefit from this precarious situation. A simple presupposition would be a greater dependence of the public on the sovereign state to remove the migrants from the parks, or an opportunity for the exploitative commercial sector to take advantage of the migrant's position outside the legal frameworks.

Davies participants further expressed a sense of abandonment and being stuck in a bureaucratic bind, when they had been coerced by the police and border authorities to move beyond the country's territories⁷⁴ In another binding effect of Necropower, per EU's Article 13, Council Regulation No. 604, "These nominally documented refugees are not permitted to register for asylum in any other EU country, for a period of at least 12 months."⁷⁵

2.5.3 *Necropeon Ethnography*

In the previous section, I justified using the term Necropeon as the means to refer to the condition of a migrant whose liveability serves the Sovereign. The Necropeon is then kept in the limbo of being an irregular migrant, by the virtue of the precarious laws which have restricted the legal avenues of liveability. This condition applies to the participants of Davies's research. Once migrants' asylum is rejected, or they've been moved from the first EU country they had arrived in, they're rendered ineligible to receive the sovereign's supports for subsistence. The migrants are coerced to move and rely on their own means for survival. Given they are also unable to legally work and eligible for asylum from another country, they're further outcasted to live as outlaws.⁷⁶ Davies notes, in a turn from biopolitical to necropolitical, the same technologies that used biometric identification to secure the

⁷² Ibid. p.1272

⁷³ Ibid.

⁷⁴ Ibid. p.1273

⁷⁵ Ibid. p.1272

⁷⁶ Ibid. p.1273

legal inclusion of the migrant, will then be used to enforce their absolute de facto exclusion from all legal frameworks. Davies also recognizes this legalistic framing as reducing refugees to bare-life.⁷⁷ Davies' concluding remarks serve as a launching pad for my research. The author's conclusion posits that inaction can be "wielded as a means of control, coercion and power"⁷⁸, whereby through carefully examining what states choose to do or not to do, we trace new footprints of structural violence – the operationalized necropolitics.

⁷⁷ Ibid.

⁷⁸ Ibid. p.1281

3. Methodology

As discussed in the aforementioned chapter, Davies's research is purely an ethnographic work that explores the avenues of Necropolitics through the perspectives and realities of the migrants, or the Necropeons. Other researchers have attempted to complement Davies's research by studying the policy frameworks surrounding the conditions that have resulted in the phenomena he explores in Calais. The gap in Davies's research is the opaque "Bureaucratic Entrapment", which serves as a Blackbox for political scientists to unwrap.

The objective of this research is to contribute to this knowledge gap by utilizing ethnography, along with methodologies of policy analysis. Similar works could be anticipated for future scholars, given the growing trend to investigate the phenomena of migration and forced migration, through conceptualizing actions and decisions within the frameworks of Necropolitics. Ergo, beyond contributing to the research gap in investigating policies of institutional violence, my work will also contribute to setting the bedrock of how future research in this field must be undertaken. The strengths, the weaknesses, and the totality of the appropriated methodologies will be assessed, challenged, and tested to better scrutinize Necropolitical frameworks of migration. More than academic contributions, this paper aspires to explore the contradictions between migration policies and practices experienced by the subjects of the policies, to assist future policy analysts and policymakers avert the in-dignification and dehumanization of individuals.

3.1 Posthuman Blackbox

Necropolitical studies sit on the abode of the anticipated posthumanist approaches to social science, where the agencies which must be held accountable in the modern political systems transcend our conventional understanding of mere networks and agencies. Posthumanism explores a greater dimension of human processes through phenomenology – the study of phenomena and the essence of experiences.

In another research I had previously conducted on unwrapping another political Blackbox in the posthuman analytical framework for the utilities of AI in Algorithmic Governance⁷⁹, I diversified my methodology toolbox with post-positivist approaches such as phenomenology, agential-realism, anthropology, and cross-case ethnography. The choice of these methods in unwrapping the Blackbox was due to their ability to create a space of knowledge that remains expansive and inclusive to future testable theories.

The results of using these methods were creating an exhaustive understanding of the process of how a phenomenon comes to fruition. While the research had a small population of participants, the depth analysis of their experiences helped with identifying the unifying attributes which corresponded to taking the first steps in unwrapping a sociopolitical Blackbox. Given my familiarity with these methodologies, in this chapter, I express confidence in reapplying similar methodologies in investigating the operationalization of necropolitics.

⁷⁹ Ardehi, Borna. *Algorithmic Governance as the foundation of posthuman politics*, 2021.

3.2 Studying Operationalization

Per the works of Davies and Mbembe, the study of Necropolitics is constituted as the study of institutional and structural violence. Following Davies's approach, violence is defined by the damage or injury inflicted on the individual through action or inaction. Even policies of humanitarian appeasement, such as caging and housing in undignified conditions are posited by Davies to act as slow violence – delayed destruction.⁸⁰

Referencing the works of Betts, Haddad, and Fitzgerald now provides a new institutional understanding as to *Why* and *which* policies are implemented for the *refugees* by the *sovereigns*. The “*How*” and the “*Why*” a sovereign constitutes legislation resulting in delayed or immediate destruction of the subject is the objective of this research. Establishing the Sovereign in this context as the U.S. government, and the subjects as the Necropeons, the central question of this research reads:

How is Necropolitics operationalized in the United States' migration policy?

Investigating the answer to this question will serve to provide scholarly knowledge on what policies are primarily implemented within the Necropolitical framework, and secondly how these policies are experienced by the subjects. The matter of operationalization is amalgamated between the two layers of policy implementation and policy execution. Thus, as the subsequent sections will further explore, the research is equipped with two general research methods:

1. Policy Analysis – to understand *how* and *why* policies are constructed within *Necropolitical frames*
2. Ethnography – to understand *how* policies are *operationalized* in the field of *migration* from the migrants' perspective

⁸⁰ Thom Davies, et al. *Violent Inaction*, 1270

3.3 Theory

Given the foundation of this research is based on examining the presence of an observed theory in an empirical phenomenon, it is safe to categorize this paper as a theory-driven scientific inquiry. Furthermore, given the intrinsic structure of this research is about studying processes and extrapolating their future outcomes, we can entangle abductive reasoning to yield greater extrapolations based on the findings.

Using variables and hypotheses is not quintessential in a theory-driven approach – and thus neither is the anticipation of generalized results. On the contrary, they're quite detrimental to the processes of studying phenomena. Instead of using variables, phenomenology in this research studies the *essence* of *phenomena* by *interpreting* the *experiences* of people who've been engaged with it. The theoretical foundation of this research takes lead from Davies' conclusion and incorporates the neologism of Necropeon within the conceptual frameworks of sovereign subject relations.

The theory reads: *Necropolitical frameworks in migration policy are operationalized through laboring the Necropeons for the sovereign's consolidation.*

The deconstruction of the theory follows this 3-step logic:

1. The U.S. government consolidates its sovereignty over residents of an invaded country. This is accomplished through creating policies of survivability dependence. Then, the subjects who were aligned with the U.S. government will remain dependent on the U.S.'s sovereign protection within internal and hyper-externalized territories of the U.S.;
2. The policies implemented by the U.S. government within these territories, then entrap the subjects in legal conundrums, which further restrains the subjects' individual freedom on the sovereign's will;
3. The subjects' survivability dependence on the sovereign, is conceptualized as Necropeon, where the Necropeon unconditionally serves and strengthens the sovereign's consolidation within internal and externalized territories.

3.4 Methodology Roadmap

Exploring the 4 stages of theory deploys 3 empirical research methods:

3.4.1 *Comparative policy analysis*

The first stage, studying policies of survivability utilizes cross-case analysis and comparative policy analysis. During the first stage, this research examines the policies the U.S. constructed in Indochina, during its foreign military expeditions. Given U.S.'s policy outcome in Afghanistan has led to the country retaining the name "Graveyard of Empires" and the "Second Vietnam", studying the case of Indochina, the U.S.-Vietnam war, opens a peripheral knowledge on what migration policies were constituted for the Vietnamese seeking American refuge.

This segment serves as an introductory section for the subsequent components of the empirical research, by briefly identifying unifying features of the policies, their drawbacks, and the extent to which they could be interpreted within Necropolitical frameworks.

3.4.2 *Interpretive Policy analysis*

The interpretive policy analysis method provides the most sophisticated toolbox for studying policies and outcomes. Through employing the performative and discursive approaches, interpretive policy analysis scrutinizes the language of the policies, the intent of the policymakers, and the intended outcome the policy was out to produce over those on its receiving end. Chapter 2.4.6 Legal Accountabiliuty articulated how the necropolitical framework and bureaucratic entrapment could serve the interests of the Neo-neo policymakers, through restricting migration and consolidating sovereignty. Studying the third stage of the theory pertains to this exact assumption and requires deploying a policy analysis method which studies a greater spectrum of how policies are constituted.

Dvora Yanow's extensive work on conducting interpretive policy analysis describes the interpretive approach to "focus on the meanings that policies have for a broad range of policy-relevant publics, including but not limited to clients and potential clients, legislators, cognate agencies [...], implementers [...], and potential voters"⁸¹ Interpretive methods are constructed on the presupposition that laws, as ambiguous as they ought to be, are characterized by possibilities of multiple interpretation and intention. No migration policy explicitly demands snaring migrants into a byzantine legal procedure where they suffer to the point of repulsion. Thus, the interpretive method provides peripheries to enable examining these impressions, if this is how they're experienced by the subjects of the policies.

⁸¹ Dvora Yanow. ,*Conducting Interpretive Policy Analysis*, 2000, p.9

Interpretive methods also help with examining the framing of policies, where we explore the “truth” constituted by the policy, rather than what it “says” in explicit language.⁸² Analysis of the “truth” in policies doesn’t pertain to a fatalistic view of what the real intent of the policy is, but rather how its “truth” is interpreted by the policy’s stakeholders. Did the Neo-neo policymakers deliberately hamper migration through obstructionist policies? Do the seemingly humanitarian policies construct entrapments?

Identification of frame is primarily deployed through identifying symbolic artifacts of a policy – who has sculpted it, why it was sculpted, what symbol the policy served for its stonemason, and what symbol it serves for its subjects, the interpretive community.⁸³ Symbols are meanings interpreted from policies; the abstraction that constructs the relationship between the sovereign and the subjects.

Complementary to the ethnographic chapter, the interpretive method deploys phenomenology to identify the policy artifacts and the frame. According to Yanow, “Interpretive philosophies, such as phenomenology and hermeneutics, contend that human meanings, values, beliefs, and feelings are embodied in and transmitted through artifacts of human creation, such as language [...] In the context of policy analysis, this means focusing on policy or agency artifacts as the concrete symbols representing more abstract policy and organizational meanings.”⁸⁴

In the explicit implementation, this paper studies the policies as cognitive artifacts. We examine their frame, by what do they mean and represent for the policymakers? What objectives are they ought to accomplish? How do the discrepancies and other related policies relate to it? Most importantly, we interpret whether the policies are constructed to deliberately entrap migrants through bureaucratic work.

3.4.3 Posthuman Performativity

In the first breakaway from academic conventions, I will incorporate theories of posthuman performativity and agential-realism into the exegesis of interpretive policy analysis. Adopted from my own previous research and the works of scholars, Barad⁸⁵This method acknowledges the dynamism of sovereigns and subjects. Posthuman performativity does not examine the role of policies as a means of interaction between the subject and the sovereign:

Instead of assuming the U.S. government constructs a static frame for the migrants to adhere to, we also process how the policy frame changes with the dynamics of the migration. Thus, the deployed

⁸² Ibid., p.16

⁸³ Ibid., p.23

⁸⁴ Ibid., p.16

⁸⁵ Posthumanist Performativity, 2003

methodology accounts for the ontological entanglement of intra-acting agencies, which reciprocally transform each other on their contact. Migrant contact with established policy frames change the policies, which then changes the dynamics of migration – a dynamic loop.

For the third stage, to determine whether the sovereign's consolidation of authority is valid insofar as the necropeon is subjected to its necropower, extend the aforementioned posthuman performativity to our ethnographic methods.

3.4.3 Phenomenological Ethnography

Phenomenological ethnography is an umbrella term adopted for a myriad of methodologies with key unifying elements. Firstly, in Heideggerian terms, the method interprets participants as Dasein within Ontics. Ontic is the phenomenon that is real and occurring – such as migration, and social movement. Dasein is the decoupling of an essence of experiences from their agents, and studying them within the context of the Ontic – such as sense of entrapment, suffering, surviving, etc. In this approach “meanings exist only insofar as they are experienced by a specific and concrete consciousness.”⁸⁶ Secondly, the researcher is immersed in the spatial and temporal condition of the participants, through semi-structured interviews and minimal engagement where the participants and ethnographer create rapport for free and open expression of emotions, interpretations, and awareness of their spatiotemporal condition. Thirdly, the approach studies essences as “how” they come into constructing the phenomena, rather than abstractions and “what” they are. We accomplish this through maximum depth and minimum research structure principles.

Given phenomenological ethnography largely uses a small participant population from different backgrounds and different experiences, I will also strongly rely on establishing epistemological holism. This embryonic ethnographic method applies individual pieces of knowledge to construct a holistic structure of phenomena experienced by participants. This entails finding unifying elements and features in individual experiences with the migration policies to reconstruct how the operationalization of policies is interpreted and experienced by the migrants.

The studied phenomenon in this context is Necropolitics. The ethnographic component pertains to studying the relevant essences and experiences where one, the necropeon, senses closer proximity to death, suffering, and survival dependency. In this virtue, and the second breakaway from academic conventions, if this research is ought to create a paradigm for further inquiry of the Necropolitical and Necropeon, the adopted methodology could arguably be Necrography: Study of individuals under institutional and operationalized violence.

⁸⁶ Barry Cooper, *Phenomenology and Political Science* (Canadian Journal of Political and Social Theory/Revue canadienne de theorie politique et sociale, Vol. V, No. 3 , 1981). p.101

3.5 Sourcing

Sourcing of policies for the comparative policy analysis and interpretive policy analysis was primarily done through official U.S. government portals, such as the Whitehouse Press (whitehouse.gov), the National Archives (archives.gov), the U.S. Department of State (state.gov), and the Refugee Processing Centre (wrapsnet) website. Through advanced search options in the U.S. Congress websites (congress.gov), I sourced the particular and relevant bills concerning Afghan migration. Open Secrets organization (opensecrets.org) was used to trace the lobbying behind the shortlisted bills.

Other official sources include publications of U.S. Citizenship and Immigration Services (uscis.gov), Homeland Security (dhs.gov), Refugee Council of U.S.A, Sponsor Circle; policy analysis institutions, such as RAND, Stanford SLS, The Conversation Journal, and reputable tabloids providing an assessment of implemented policies.

Sourcing for the Ethnographic component of the research was dominantly restricted by primary accessibility and ethical barriers. With the internet and landline services being either inaccessible or infrequently accessible, the communication with the participants lacked consistency. While I hoped to construct a chronology of their experiences through the processes, this option was not possible. To access the Afghans situated in the migration camps, I used the hashtag filters in social media to access the posts submitted by refugees from these camps. For instance by searching for #AIUdaid, #RamsteinCamp, #Afghanrefugees, etc. After building rapport through consistent communication and explaining the objective of this research, a number of them agreed to share their experiences from the camps.

Through my prior experience with an Afghan refugee center based in Malaysia, Pandawas academy, I was able to find contacts and participants who were able and willing to share their experiences. Direct communications were done through chats, sending voicemails, video logs, and phone calls, where the option was possible. Given my personal proximity to Iran, and the presence of over 3 million Afghan refugees in the country, I established rapport with both refugee centers as well as individual Afghans, whose relatives were undergoing the migration process. Individual Afghans incorporated into this research were irregular migrants in Iran, some of whom had been employed in an acquaintance's factory in Tehran. The latter process pertained to outsourcing my participant observation to a third person, who shared the experiences of known relatives and friends who were undergoing the migration process. The authenticity of their experiences was only verified through screenshots and shared voice memos.

I also established communication with several migrants outside Afghanistan and within the camps, through their previous participation in press and journals, and mutual acquaintances. These participants verified their migration status during video blogs by sharing footage of the camps and facilities.

Due to a lack of available resources, there was a limited option of choosing participants from many diverse demographic and social backgrounds. As such, the majority of the participants were Persian speakers originating from Kabul and Herat. They include military personnel, bankers, interpreters, contractors, and relatives of those who had already migrated to the U.S. For obvious ethical and security means, the participants will remain anonymous. In total, the findings are based on 53 hours of interviews with 38 participants, 4 of whom were engaged in greater depth.

The communications were in Persian and English, for the case of the interpreters. Given both languages are my native tongues, the discursive phenomenology and assessment of experiences were void of language barriers.

4. The Oracle and The Odyssey

Pythia, the oracle of Delphi, baned many Greek heroes and heroines through the prophecies to reveal the divine truth and pathways of endeavors journeys. Yet, unknown to the Heroes, many of Oracle's vaticinations were poised by the intervention of the Olympian gods. The twelve labors of Heracles were entertainment for Hera, the sister-wife of Zeus. Many odysseys in Greek mythology present the same ethos – the struggle of subjects for the entertainment of the sovereign. Yet, while the oracles were determined and set by the sovereigns, the subjects, through Promethean spirit, rebelled or invented routes to bypass the most dreading obstacles of the Odyssey. When the gods tempered with the oracles to indurate the journey, the protagonists responded in kind and adjusted to the challenges.

This chapter explores the dynamics of sovereign and subject relations from the vistas of the Oracles and Odyssey. The policies, precedents, and bureaucracy determine the migration routes, presenting the determined oracle – medium of Sovereign's entertainment. The Odyssey is the migration route undertaken by the migrating subjects.

Chapter four begins with exploring the historical context of the Afghan odyssey, and the extent to which it could be used to extrapolate the most recent wave of Afghan migration. The first section delves into the journey of Afghan migrants prior to the U.S. withdrawal from the country

The subsequent sections digest the crux of the original oracle – policies, and legal avenues of migration set by the U.S. government prior to the withdrawal. The rite of passage examines the initial plan for granting refuge and resettling asylum seekers. This section further addresses the historical precedents of similar policies implemented during the country's withdrawal from Indochina. Exploration of the historical context of these policies determines the premise of whether the Necropolitical frame has been a recurring tool for the U.S.'s migration policies.

The final section, Katabasis, provides extensive empirical work on ethnography and policy analysis, by examining the evacuation process, the intermezzo, and the settlement process from the perspectives of both migrants and policy commentators.

4.1 Exodus

The contemporary memory of Afghanistan shrouds the nation under the fog of a perpetual state of conflict – a nation displaced. Understanding the exodus of the Afghans and the historical contingent of migration, gives readers an analytical understanding of the dynamic nature of the country's sovereignty, and provides a logical prelude to conceptualizing the Afghans as a nation with more than a single sovereign. This understanding also creates further groundings to understand migration as an institutionalized normative component of the Afghan realities.

Prior to the Soviet invasion of Afghanistan, migratory movements between Afghanistan, Iran and Pakistan were recurring phenomena. Safri's study of migration transformation of Afghans, traces the mass scale migration to 1850s, "when 5,000 Hazara families settled in Jam and Bakharz in Iran and another 168,000 from 1880-1903"⁸⁷ With the oil boom of the 1950s, and the opportunity to receive higher wages in mass urbanization construction projects in Iran, many male Afghans migrated westward.⁸⁸ This process remained an organic phenomena of international migration, until 1979, when the first cases of mass refuge appeared following the Soviet invasion.

4.1.1 *The Four Sovereigns of Migration*

The Afghan survival migration from 1979 onwards can be divided in four phases, each traced to an unconsolidated Sovereign. The first wave began during the Soviet invasion. Although many Afghans left the country for their own safety, the conflict between Afghan Soldiers, the Soviet soldiers, and the newly-established Mujahideen greatly destabilized the country.⁸⁹ While the ensued disabilities and inaccessibility of livability conditions created incentives of survival migration, the establishment of the Soviet puppet regime in Afghanistan gave religious incentives for the others.

The "Hijra" is an Arabic word for "migration". A spiritual decree to embark on a Hijra is evoked when the country of the muslim has been taken over by the Kufars, or non-followers of Islam. The Soviet puppet government separation of church and state and establishment of secular policies, provoked the dominantly Muslim and conservative population of Afghanistan.⁹⁰ The first Hijra in Islam took place by Prophet Muhammed, when he migrated from Mecca to Medina, in an objection to submitting to the sovereignty of a non-Islamic authority. Thus, the phenomena of migration for the Afghans in 1979 was

⁸⁷ Maliha Safri, "The Transformation of the Afghan Refugee: 1979–2009," *The Middle East Journal* 65, no. 4 (2011): pp. 587-601, <https://doi.org/10.3751/65.4.14>. P. 596

⁸⁸ Ibid.

⁸⁹ Francis Fukuyama, "Pakistan since the Soviet Invasion of Afghanistan," 1982, <https://doi.org/10.21236/ada111442>.

⁹⁰ Dale F. Eickelman and James Piscatori, *Muslim Travellers: Pilgrimage, Migration and the Religious Imagination* (Routledge, 2013). p.40

⁹¹ M. Nazif Shahrani, "Ten. Afghanistan's Muhajirin (Muslim 'Refugee-Warriors'): Politics of Mistrust and Distrust of Politics," *Mistrusting Refugees*, 1995, pp. 187-206, <https://doi.org/10.1525/9780520341234-013>.

a normative institution and objective refusal to submit to the territorial sovereign. The desitnation of migration during Hijra is towards another territory governed by a Muslim sovereign – namely Iran and Pakistan. This single precedent sets an example of how dynamic the nature of sovereignty presented itself even in the first wave of Afghan survival migration. In the process of Hijra, both Iran and Pakistan were welcoming of the Afghans, on the precedent of religious customs.⁹²

During the same period, the first case of Necropeonage was incorporated in the Iranian migration policies, when the surge of petrodollars created a demand for low-wage necropeons in construction, mining, brick-burning and other survival jobs.⁹³ Afghan refugees were quickly incorporated in the country's labor pool and restricted to manual labor. With the exacerbated labor shortage as the result of the Iraq-Iran war, many Labour laws were alleviated to reduce bureaucratic burden of granting Afghans with work permits.⁹⁴⁹⁵

The second wave of Afghan migration involved primarily those who collaborated with the Soviet Unions. This included the government officials, military personnel, translators, and those who expressed support for the communist ideology. The deposed president and this category of migrants were categorically denied to use the Hijra privileges, and so the majority migrated towards Russia and India.⁹⁶⁹⁷⁹⁸ The power vacuum following the soviet withdrawal, resulted in the 1989 Afghan civil war. The devastating results of power grab by various regional warlords, exacerbated to a refugee crisis – internally and externally.⁹⁹

This case would have provided an excellent opportunity to assess the parallels it posits with the migration occurring after the U.S. withdrawal from the county. However, insufficiency of resources and language barrier restrict further investigation into analyzing historical conformity of collaborators survival migration.

The third wave of migration began in 1994 with the takeover of the Mujahideen's successor state, the Taliban. The end of the civil war began with the consolidation of the Afghan Islamic emirate and a bottom-up process of state building. Consolidation of sovereignty was accelerated with the popular

⁹² Ibid.

⁹³ Ibid. p. 590

⁹⁴ Ibid.

⁹⁵ Farhad Darvishi and Mehdi Rahmati, “(بررسی روابط ایران و شوروی در دوره جنگ تحمیلی (با تاکید بر مسئله افغانستان) [Examining the Soviet-Iranian Relations during the Iran-Iraq War (with Attention to Afghanistan)],” *Holy Defense Studies* 2, no. 1 (2015): pp. 35-55, https://doi.org/https://hds.sndu.ac.ir/article_1665.html.

⁹⁶ Kathleen Newland and Erin Patrick, “A Nation Displaced: The World's Largest Refugee Population.,” *Migration Policy Institute*, 2001, <https://doi.org/http://www.migrationpolicy.org/pubs/displaced.php>.

⁹⁷ Anne-Sophie Bentz, “Afghan Refugees in Indo-Afghan Relations,” *Cambridge Review of International Affairs* 26, no. 2 (2013): pp. 374-391, <https://doi.org/10.1080/09557571.2013.785094>.

⁹⁸ Nithya Rajan, “‘No Afghan Refugees in India’: Refugees and Cold War Politics in the 1980s,” *South Asia: Journal of South Asian Studies* 44, no. 5 (2021): pp. 851-867, <https://doi.org/10.1080/00856401.2021.1964048>.

⁹⁹ Kathleen Newland and Erin Patrick, “A Nation Displaced: The World's Largest Refugee Population.,” *Migration Policy Institute*, 2001, <https://doi.org/http://www.migrationpolicy.org/pubs/displaced.php>.

support for the Taliban, who formed with good intentions¹⁰⁰¹⁰¹ to “restore peace, disarm the population, enforce Sharia law and defend the integrity and Islamic character of Afghanistan.”¹⁰² Sovereignty as discussed in the works of Fitzgerald and Haddad, is sustained not with mere need and support of the subjects, but also with reciprocal recognition of the sovereign by other sovereigns, and the responsibilities to ensure the well-being of all citizens, with respect to their human rights.

Internationally, they were only recognized by Pakistan, Saudi Arabia and the United Arab Emirates. Domestically, Taliban’s sovereignty was challenged from the very beginning due to their incompetencies in governance of resources, and the inhuman restrictions and persecution the state enacted against women and minorities to homogenize the nation under totality of Islamic Sharia sovereignty.¹⁰³ This coagulated with worsening economic and humanitarian conditions, which resulted in the displacement of 600,000 people just from Kabul.¹⁰⁴

Barnett Rubin, who has extensively studied the subject of Taliban’s sovereignty with United States Institute of Peace since the 2000s, recalls the early efforts of Taliban to integrate with the international society since their establishment:

*“In January 1997, four months after the Taliban captured Kabul, Mullah Wakil Ahmad Mutawakkil, who was then Mullah Omar’s spokesman and who later became foreign minister, led a delegation to the United Nations in New York to ask the U.N. secretary-general to grant them Afghanistan’s seat in the General Assembly. They did not realize that the secretary-general is not the emir of the U.N. and that he would be bound by the decision of the General Assembly on this question.”*¹⁰⁵

A discursive shift in Pakistan and Iran also changed the the status of Afghan survival migrants seeking refuge from the Taliban state. In 1993, Iran constituted that Afghan Muhajirin, those who were granted support under Hijra, would be articulated as “Panahandegan”, translated as “Asylum” with no customary religious protection under Islamic sovereignty.¹⁰⁶¹⁰⁷ Through this decree previously issued

¹⁰⁰ Steve Coll, *Ghost Wars: The Secret History of the CIA, Afghanistan and Bin Laden* (London: Penguin, 2005).

¹⁰¹ Zalmay Khalilzad, “Afghanistan in 1994: Civil War and Disintegration,” *Asian Survey* 35, no. 2 (January 1995): pp. 147-152, <https://doi.org/10.2307/2645023>. P. 152

¹⁰² Shannon A. Middleton, “Women’s Rights Unveiled: Taliban’s Treatment of Women in Afghanistan,” *Indiana International & Comparative Law Review* 11, no. 2 (February 2001): pp. 421-468, <https://doi.org/10.18060/17725>.. 425

¹⁰³ Shanon, p. 423

¹⁰⁴ Safri. p.601

¹⁰⁵ Barnett R. Rubin, “Leveraging the Taliban’s Quest for International Recognition,” *United States Institute of Peace*, March 2021,

https://doi.org/https://www.usip.org/sites/default/files/Afghanistan-Peace-Process_Talibans-Quest-for-International-Recognition.pdf. p.3

¹⁰⁶ Ibid. p.592

¹⁰⁷ Zalmay. p.149

permits and certificates, which granted Afghans certain rights were suspended. This arguably began the first Afghan experience with bureaucratic entrapment. The suspension of the Afghan refugee rights in Iran has the potential to be studied as its own depth-ful research within Necropolitical frameworks.

The fourth wave began with the War on Terror and the capitulation of the Taliban in 2002. The Taliban's lack of sovereign authority led to the government being left isolated from the international society.¹⁰⁸ The news articles from this period, warned of impending refugee crisis spillover as the result of the first week of the U.S.'s invasion.¹⁰⁹ While millions were displaced and flocking the borders, Iran, Pakistan, and Tajikistan closed their borders,¹¹⁰ further reinforcing the necropolitical frame of their migration policies against the Afghans.

Through the efforts of the U.S., the UN and other NATO countries, the Transitional Islamic State of Afghanistan was established in an effort to democratize the country and consolidate the Afghan government's sovereignty within the international society.¹¹¹ In 2004, the Afghan government fully consolidated itself as a legitimate sovereign in the international society and the first resettlement efforts began in the subsequent years, in the areas freed from Taliban control.¹¹² Even yet, the Afghan government didn't fully establish its sovereign authority domestically. Areas under the Taliban regime were governed by the Taliban court and their codes of justice, which were the preferred institutions for rural and conservative Afghans.¹¹³ The operationality of the Taliban court within Afghanistan's sovereignty, reinforced the institutional norm that the territory was governed by a dichotomous Sovereignty. Within this context, Afghan affairs were constituted by two separate legal courts, and two states, both lacking authority and consolidation.

¹⁰⁸ Ben Saul, "'Recognition' and the Taliban's International Legal Status," ICCT, March 29, 2022, <https://icct.nl/publication/recognition-talibans-international-legal-status/>.

¹⁰⁹ Steve Harrigan, "Afghan Refugee Crisis Spreads," CNN (Cable News Network), accessed May 13, 2022, <http://edition.cnn.com/2001/WORLD/asiapcf/central/09/20/ret.afghan.refugees/>.

¹¹⁰ Steve Harrigan, "Afghan Refugee Crisis Spreads," CNN (Cable News Network), accessed May 13, 2022, <http://edition.cnn.com/2001/WORLD/asiapcf/central/09/20/ret.afghan.refugees/>.

¹¹¹ Barnett R. Rubin, "Crafting a Constitution for Afghanistan," *Journal of Democracy* 15, no. 3 (2004): pp. 5-19, <https://doi.org/10.1353/jod.2004.0051>.

¹¹² Maliha, p.599

¹¹³ Jennifer Glasse, "Inside a Taliban Court in Afghanistan," Taliban News | Al Jazeera (Al Jazeera, January 3, 2015), <https://www.aljazeera.com/news/2015/1/3/inside-a-taliban-court-in-afghanistan>.

4.1.2 *The Fifth Sovereign*

The first theory of the research posits The U.S. government consolidated its sovereignty over residents of Afghanistan, by creating a policy of survivability dependence. Thus the subjects who were aligned with the U.S. government will remain dependent on the U.S.'s sovereign protection within internal and hyper-externalized territories of the U.S.. The phenomenon of the fifth sovereign examines this theory through the discursive study of policies and dialogues surrounding the initial Afghan-U.S. peace talks.

It is indefinite when the fifth wave of migration began. While many participants of the interviews had begun their movement with the announcement of the U.S. withdrawal from Afghanistan, others remained attentive to the situation until the 11th hour. It was anticipated by many that the government of Afghanistan would be able to withhold the Taliban. This impression was indicative of the public's lack of awareness of the dialogues and negotiations taking place between the de facto Taliban office in Doha, and the other sovereigns of the International society.

Since 2007, the Taliban embarked on a mission of attaining international recognition as a movement, in an attempt to attain recognition, and clear the group's name from the sanction lists.¹¹⁴ Rubin writes, that the Taliban have learned where they failed in the past, and sought a post-settlement Afghan Islamic government, wherein they'd hold substantial and dominant positions.¹¹⁵ The Taliban's plea for recognition stems from their awareness of their state fragility and inability to function the country without the U.S.'s foreign aid – essentially they can never “outwait the United States' unwillingness to give aid.”¹¹⁶

The Taliban were well aware that negotiating political inclusion with the Afghani government and infusion of Sovereign authority would be impossible without the U.S.'s consent.¹¹⁷ The initial rounds of dialogues with the U.S. and international partners were based on creating a premise for this political integration and settlement after U.S.'s withdrawal. However, the group's insistence on their claim to be “Islamic Emirate” even before the capitulation of the Afghan government thwarted much of their efforts to gain recognition as a political movement.¹¹⁸ During the Trump administration, the mood of the dialogues shifted from post-settlement government to creating corridors for U.S. withdrawal.

The U.S.'s decision for swift withdrawal, initiated by Trump, didn't give legal space for creating a consolidated Sovereign for a post-settlement government. Amid these dialogues, the Afghan

¹¹⁴ Rubin, p.2

¹¹⁵ Ibid.

¹¹⁶ Ibid.

¹¹⁷ Ibid. p.5

¹¹⁸ Ibid. p.8

government and the nation were starkly divided to entertain the dialogue of inclusion with the Taliban for a peaceful settlement.

All past four waves of migration were confined to the entanglement of unconsolidated sovereignty. Subjects who were involved in the fifth wave of migration precisely lacked the space to determine a sovereign. The dependence of the Afghan government on the U.S. government to engage in dialogues with the Taliban for a peaceful settlement extends the sovereign protection of Afghan subjects to the U.S.'s suzerainty. Thus, even prior to the U.S.'s withdrawal from Afghanistan, we may posit the argument that the de facto sovereign of the Afghan people was the U.S. government. In the same virtue, the Afghan population was subjected to another duo of sovereigns simultaneously – both the U.S. and the Afghan government.

The U.S., acting as the suzerain over the Afghan government's sovereignty, held the withdrawal dialogues with the Taliban without engaging the Afghan government, a move vehemently protested by President Ghani.¹¹⁹ A dialogue that was supposed to take place in Camp David with the presence of President Ghani, President Trump and the Taliban delegation, was later dubbed “dead” by President Trump, after a terrorist attack in Kabul left an American casualty. Previously, when the Taliban had also realized the talks would be trilateral, they responded “we do not recognize the stooge government” in Kabul.”¹²⁰

This must have been alert to the U.S. policymakers to secure a reconciliation protocol in establishing a unified sovereign in Afghanistan. Insistence on the withdrawal, delayed dialogues on a post-settlement government, and the sudden change of policy to focus on withdrawing U.S. troops without intra-Afghan dialogues, easily extrapolated Afghanistan's inevitable demise.

The same position, to withdraw American troops from Afghanistan regardless of the peace deal with Taliban, was also echoed by electoral oppositions to President Trump, namely Sen. Buffet and Mayor Buttigieg. During the electoral primaries,¹²¹ Sen. Buffet justified the decision with “it is not helping the safety and security of Afghanistan.”¹²² For both the Democratic and Republicans, withdrawal from

¹¹⁹ Peter Baker, Mujib Mashal, and Michael Crowley, “How Trump's Plan to Secretly Meet with the Taliban Came Together, and Fell Apart,” *The New York Times* (The New York Times, September 9, 2019), <https://www.nytimes.com/2019/09/08/world/asia/afghanistan-trump-camp-david-taliban.html>.

¹²⁰ Ibid.

¹²¹ Ellen Mitchell, “Buttigieg, Warren Pledge Afghanistan Withdrawal Even without Taliban Peace Deal,” *The Hill* (The Hill, September 13, 2019), <https://thehill.com/homenews/campaign/461236-buttigieg-warren-pledge-afghanistan-withdrawal-even-without-taliban-peace/>.

¹²² Ellen Mitchell, “Buttigieg, Warren Pledge Afghanistan Withdrawal Even without Taliban Peace Deal,” *The Hill* (The Hill, September 13, 2019), <https://thehill.com/homenews/campaign/461236-buttigieg-warren-pledge-afghanistan-withdrawal-even-without-taliban-peace/>.

Afghanistan was a promising electoral victory. The framing of the policy was constituted on the grounds of not wasting American lives and taxpayer money.

While many policy makers iterated the inevitability of Taliban takeover and government capitulation,¹²³¹²⁴¹²⁵¹²⁶ The U.S. government under the Biden administration insisted on having full trust in the capabilities of the Afghan military to sustain itself and the state. In the July 8th Press, when questioned with “our own intelligence community has assessed that the Afghan government will likely collapse”¹²⁷, President Biden responds with “That’s not true”¹²⁸, followed by “ they didn’t — did not reach that conclusion.”¹²⁹

During the same press conference, President Biden was questioned whether he would trust handing the government to the Taliban, to which he responded with “No. But I trust the capacity of the Afghan military, who is better trained, better equipped, and more re- — more competent in terms of conducting war”¹³⁰ When asked whether the last 20 years were worth the billions and the lives lost, President Biden’s response echoed George President Bush’s “Mission Accomplished” speech, before the eruption of Iraqi civil war after capitulation of Saddam: “We accomplished both of those objectives — period.”¹³¹ said President Biden, with reference to taking out Osama Bin Laden and debilitating Al Qaeda. President Biden further argued, “no nation has ever unified Afghanistan. No nation. Empires have gone there and not done it”¹³² which hinted to the inevitability of escalation of the conflicts — demonstrating the president’s awareness of the impending doom.

Biden’s press was poised with dissonance on the status of the U.S. in relation to the sovereignty of Afghanistan. Initially he iterated “The Afghan government and leadership has to come together. They clearly have the capacity to sustain the government in place”¹³³, expressing trust in Afghan

¹²³ David E. Sanger and Mujib Mashal, “After Trump Calls off Talks, Afghanistan Braces for Violence,” *The New York Times* (The New York Times, September 8, 2019), <https://www.nytimes.com/2019/09/08/us/politics/pompeo-trump-afghan-peace-negotiations.html>.

¹²⁴ Natasha Lindstaedt and Nawid Tanha, “Afghanistan: Taliban Victory Inevitable despite the Trillions the U.S. Poured In,” *The Conversation*, May 5, 2022, <https://theconversation.com/afghanistan-taliban-victory-inevitable-despite-the-trillions-the-us-poured-in-166060>.

¹²⁵ Natasha Turak, “Afghanistan's War Will Spread beyond Its Borders as Taliban Advances, Senior Negotiator Warns,” *CNBC* (CNBC, August 12, 2021), <https://www.cNBC.com/2021/08/11/afghanistan-war-will-spread-beyond-its-borders-top-negotiator-warns.html>.

¹²⁶ Al Jazeera, “Pakistan Useful for Us Only to Clean up Afghanistan 'Mess': Khan,” *Imran Khan News | Al Jazeera* (Al Jazeera, August 12, 2021), <https://www.aljazeera.com/news/2021/8/12/pakistan-imran-khan-afghanistan-mess-taliban>.

¹²⁷ The White House Press, “Remarks by President Biden on the Drawdown of U.S. Forces in Afghanistan,” *The White House* (The United States Government, July 8, 2021),

<https://www.whitehouse.gov/briefing-room/speeches-remarks/2021/07/08/remarks-by-president-biden-on-the-drawdown-of-u-s-forces-in-afghanistan/>.

¹²⁸ *Ibid.*

¹²⁹ *Ibid.*

¹³⁰ *Ibid.*

¹³¹ *Ibid.*

¹³² *Ibid.*

¹³³ *Ibid.*

government's consolidation of its sovereign authority, followed by "the only way there's ultimately going to be peace and security in Afghanistan is that [Afghan government] work out a modus vivendi with the Taliban and they make a judgment as to how they can make peace."¹³⁴

In assessing this phenomenon, with consideration to the discrepancies in President Biden's claims and the awareness of the U.S. intelligence, I postulate that U.S. policymakers were fully aware of the inevitable takeover of the Taliban. Thus the policies framed under the pretense of defending American security and lives, were also deliberately constructed with immediate disparities which prevented stable institutional consolidation in Afghanistan.

With either prospect of civil war, or the reemergence of the second Emirate, the inaction of the U.S. policies to consolidate an agreement between the states, set the foundation for the future Afghanistan policies to be established on the crux of Necropolitical frameworks. The next section builds the argument of how the fifth sovereign was indeed constructed with the means to create necropolitical phenomena.

4.1.3 The Doha Agreement

The second argument I posit, states the Doha peace agreement in 2020 had consolidated the Taliban as the de facto sovereign over Afghanistan, by committing the group to key responsibilities associated with the sovereign. Per the conditions of the agreement, the Taliban would never receive de jure sovereign recognition outside intra-Afghan dialogues with the government of Afghanistan. Thus, affirming the first theory, which contends, the U.S. created policies of survivability dependence, and the need for subjects for the U.S.'s sovereign protection, thereby consolidating the U.S.'s externalized sovereignty.

The Doha agreement signed on February 29, 2020, emphasized the importance of intra-Afghan dialogues as a prelude to reaching a peace agreement between the U.S. and the Taliban.¹³⁵ In good faith to begin the Intra-Afghan dialogue, the first part of the agreement concurred to the "expeditiously release combat and political prisoners as a confidence-building measure with the coordination and approval of all relevant sides."¹³⁶ Although previously the Taliban regime had refused to negotiate with the Afghan government in the reluctance of recognizing its sovereignty, this time the dialogues were thwarted by the Afghan government. The U.S., per the agreement, *committed* to working with all sides. Since the agreement was void of any mention of the Afghan government, per the Taliban's insistence,

¹³⁴ *Ibid.*

¹³⁵ U.S. Department of States, "Agreement for Bringing Peace to Afghanistan between the Islamic Emirate of Afghanistan Which Is Not Recognized by the United States as a State and Is Known as the Taliban and the United States of America," 2020.

¹³⁶ *Ibid.*

the Afghan government then rejected the prison releases, stating “The government of Afghanistan has made no commitment to free 5,000 Taliban prisoners”¹³⁷ followed by “It is not in the authority of the United States to decide, they are only a facilitator.”¹³⁸ The Afghan government had recognized its lack of sovereign authority, and its late-stage attempt to consolidate the role by undermining the U.S.’s authority, inadvertently doomed the prospects of intra-Afghan relations. To the Taliban, the terms were also clear the agreement was binding until the U.S.’s withdrawal from the region. Here the old adage, ‘You have the watches, we have the time’ was credited to the Taliban. Upon U.S.’s withdrawal, it wouldn’t matter if the Afghan government had released the prisoners – the Taliban would consolidate itself as the government.

The first part of the agreement determined two key initiations from the U.S.: Along with the withdrawal of the troops, the start of the intra-Afghan dialogues would also embark on U.S.’s initiation to review the current U.S. sanctions over the Taliban with the goal of relief by August 2020. Secondly, this initiation would be extended to the Security Council by May 2020.¹³⁹

The second part of the agreement primarily focused on the responsibilities of the Taliban in creating the security perimeters for the U.S.’s withdrawal, along with the securitization of internal migrants.¹⁴⁰ The treaty committed the Taliban to adhere to the International Migration Law, by “dealing with those seeking asylum or residence in Afghanistan.”¹⁴¹ Per classical Weberian terms, the state has the monopoly on violence. Thus, by trusting Afghanistan with security peripheries across the regions including the capital, the U.S. had granted the monopoly of statehood to the Taliban. Additionally, citing the works of Haddad, the migrants are dependent on Sovereigns, as Sovereigns on the migrants for recognition. By employing the Taliban to “deal with those seeking asylum” the treaty made no inclusion of the Afghan government, and created a deliberate linkage of subject-sovereign between the Afghans and the Taliban. Outrageously, the agreement also urged the Taliban to impede from issuing passports to certain individuals. A Passport is a sovereign artifact, which extends the sovereign protection for subjects beyond the territories of the sovereign nation. The loose language in the agreement could be interpreted to imply the inevitability of the Taliban issuing sovereign passports for

¹³⁷ Al Jazeera, “Afghan President Rejects Prisoner Swap with the Taliban,” Taliban News | Al Jazeera (Al Jazeera, March 1, 2020), <https://www.aljazeera.com/news/2020/3/1/president-ghani-rejects-peace-deals-prisoner-swap-with-taliban>.

¹³⁸ Ibid.

¹³⁹ “With the start of intra-Afghan negotiations, the United States will initiate an administrative review of current U.S. sanctions and the rewards list against members of the Islamic Emirate of Afghanistan which is not recognized by the United States as a state and is known as the Taliban with the goal of removing these sanctions by August 27, 2020 [...] With the start of intra-Afghan negotiations, the United States will start diplomatic engagement with other members of the United Nations Security Council and Afghanistan to remove members of the Islamic Emirate of Afghanistan which is not recognized by the United States as a state and is known as the Taliban from the sanctions list with the aim of achieving this objective by May 29, 2020” Ibid.

¹⁴⁰ Ibid.

¹⁴¹ Ibid.

the Afghan subjects. With the authority granted to the Taliban by the U.S., they'd also be the hurdle for the Afghans to access the international society – the embodied Hippocratic bubble.

We may ponder whether the fifth Sovereign is then a reference to the second emirate of the Taliban. To that end, I reluctantly argue that it isn't: the fifth state is the U.S. government which created the conditions of survival dependence. If the intra-Afghans never proceeded –which was expected– the sanctions over the Taliban would not have been lifted. Worse, if the Afghan government was to capitulate, the U.S. would extend the sanctions and freeze Afghan assets at large. As discussed in the previous section, the Taliban are well aware of their fragility and inability to function in the country without U.S.'s foreign aid. Thus liveability of the Afghans under the Taliban sovereignty is bound to the de facto externalized sovereignty of the U.S. – which I will daringly posit to be the territories of Afghanistan. The Taliban will not be a recognized sovereign, without the framework of sovereign recognition determined by the U.S..

4.1.3 Leave To Live

Having realized the temporal limits of the binding Doha agreement, and the reluctance of the Afghan government to comply with the agreement, the Taliban began its southern offensive to violently consolidate its position across Afghanistan.¹⁴² The attacks were escalated in the coming months¹⁴³ in a brutalization of hundreds of Afghan military personnel wounded and killed.¹⁴⁴ This transitioned the national mood of the coming changes from that of desperate hope of peace and settlement governance, to another violent takeover of Afghanistan by the Taliban. Every participant in this research carried a cognitive scar, a memory of the Taliban's mass executions and hanging across the streets in Kabul and Herat. The Hazaras recalled losing relatives to bombings of mosques. Young women recalled the paranoia of their families in protecting them during their grown-ups. The rampant takeover of Afghanistan was also followed by an inconsolable fear of targeted killings of military personnel, journalists, activists, government officials, and interpreters.

The Haqqani Network, which operated as the intelligent arm of the Taliban insurgencies –responsible for numerous high profile assassinations–¹⁴⁵ was rumored to have compiled a list of targeted individuals. A participant was extorted by a Taliban member to pay a ransom for having his name and

¹⁴² Reuters Person, "Taliban Launches Major Afghan Offensive after Deadline for U.S. Pullout," Reuters (Thomson Reuters, May 4, 2021),

<https://www.reuters.com/world/asia-pacific/taliban-launches-huge-afghan-offensive-after-deadline-us-pullout-2021-05-04/>.

¹⁴³ Reuters. "Over 150 Afghan Troops Killed or Injured in Last 24 Hours as Violence Mounts Ahead of Foreign Troops' Withdrawal." DAWN.COM, June 7, 2021.

<https://www.dawn.com/news/1628067/over-150-afghan-troops-killed-or-injured-in-last-24-hours-as-violence-mounts-ahead-of-foreign-troops-withdrawal>.

¹⁴⁴ Ibid.

¹⁴⁵ Mujib Mashal, "At Afghan Peace Talks, Hoping to End Their Fathers' War," The New York Times (The New York Times, October 5, 2020), <https://www.nytimes.com/2020/10/05/world/asia/afghan-peace-talks-children.html>.

his immediate family removed from the list. The fear of this threat was exacerbated to a frenzy building up to August, with the news of abductions and targeted killing sweeping the country. In the same time, New York Times reported these targeted killings¹⁴⁶ extended to family members or acquaintances of suspected collaborators. In the same report, the brother of a victim commenting on the targeted killing stated, “there was never any such thing as amnesty [...] Everyone knew he worked with the Americans.” He further added, “[U.S.] didn’t help my brother [...] they betrayed him.” given his brother had a pending special immigrant visa application.¹⁴⁷ The sense of resentment and betrayal towards the U.S. was a dominant theme, accompanied by a sense of dissonance to appeal to the U.S. to expand its special visa program. Many, fearing for their lives, migrated to Kabul. Those who were qualified for the special U.S. programs to grant visas were in an open plea to speed the process. Others moved to Oman, Iran and Pakistan. The onslaught sent a clear message: Leave to live.

Those within the security forces, military personnel, and government official, had expected the Taliban to arrive in Kabul. Participants describe a lack of general command and coordination during this period. Even those who were equipped and enabled to resist, were recommended to refrain from violent engagement with the Taliban – perhaps with the means of de-escalation, avoiding provocation, and preventative retaliation. Afghan forces were aware of their incapability to resist the Taliban without the support of the U.S.. The most dominantly capable unit, the 03 CIA-trained “Death squad”, was tasked with protecting the airport corridors for evacuees – not fending the Taliban.

Before the fall of Kabul, one of the most evident signs that the liveability of certain individuals depended on them leaving the country, was the matter of financial citizenry. To live and to survive, an individual is required to be financially maintained. Before the U.S. froze Afghan assets, Taliban members targeted the banks and other financial facilities in a hostile takeover. For those who had reserved their assets in Afghan banks, the process of them losing their accounts was absurdly simple. A banker described the process as follows: The Taliban members accessed the occupational data of individuals and filtered every member employed by the U.S. and NATO allies, or in the military and Afghan government. Just as a simple command in an excel sheet, a number of these individuals had their accounts terminated. In the blink of an eye, former military personnel described, the entire life savings vanished. Given most Afghans have large families, the financial confiscation extended the existential crisis to the family members – an act of slow targeted killing. Those who were financially paralyzed were unable to provide proof of financial assets – a requirement for obtaining any visa as an Afghan citizen. These individuals were coerced into the survival migration.

¹⁴⁶ Susannah George and Sudarsan Raghavan, “Taliban Wages Campaign of Targeted Killings against Former Members of Afghan Security Forces,” *The Washington Post* (WP Company, December 3, 2021), <https://www.washingtonpost.com/world/2021/11/30/taliban-killings-security/>.

¹⁴⁷ *Ibid.*

4.2 Entrapment

A common phrase used by the participants to describe their state of being, was “Belataklif.” While the phrase doesn’t have a direct English translation, it corresponds to the state of being without purpose due to the inability to respond to the change of circumstances or being dependent on a critical juncture to then be able to escape an indeterminate decision. The most common case of belataklif was being unable to “do anything” until it was decided whether a migrant could receive the special visa waiver. Until a decision was to be made on the visa status, the migrant behaves and operates in the abstract to maintain its basic survival functions. The state of bare-life, is described by both Davies and Mbembe. All the participants anticipated ways of survival for their families and themselves. Situated in the state of being belataklif, the survival migrants describe being trapped. Some echoed that a quick death would’ve been more merciful than undergoing this process of individual indeterminism.

Per the second theory, The policies implemented by the U.S. government within externalized territories, entrap the subjects in legal conundrums, which further restrains the subjects’ individual freedom on the sovereign’s will. Having a bird-eye view of this phenomenon, I argue the situation has been deliberately determined to be determined for the migrants. Through the sense of indeterminism, the migrant is subjected to Necropeonage, which is reserved to serve the consolidation of the sovereign. This chapter discusses the operationalization of Necropeonage through the enforced policies of the sovereign.

4.2.1 *The Second Saigon*

During the same July press conference of President Biden, one of the questions from the press was “Do you see any parallels between this withdrawal and what happened in Vietnam.”¹⁴⁸ to which President Biden responded with “None whatsoever [...] The Taliban is not the south — the North Vietnamese army [...] There’s going to be no circumstance where you see people being lifted off the roof of an embassy.”¹⁴⁹ The fall of Kabul rings many parallels and familiarities to the political consciousness of the American public and policymakers. In many ways, Afghanistan has been dubbed the second Vietnam, with the fall of Kabul echoing the fall of Saigon after the American withdrawal. South Vietnamese stormed the U.S. embassy in Saigon hoping to be evacuated. With the fall of South Vietnam being eminent, the U.S. launched Operation Frequent Wind to evacuate Americans and the Vietnamese at risk.¹⁵⁰

¹⁴⁸ The White House Press

¹⁴⁹ Ibid.

¹⁵⁰ Dave Roos, “How the End of the Vietnam War Led to a Refugee Crisis,” History.com (A&E Television Networks, September 1, 2021), <https://www.history.com/news/vietnam-war-refugees#:~:text=Over%20the%20next%20two%20decades,pirates%20or%20overcrowded%2C%20makeshift%20boats.>

What ensued afterward, was two decades and three million people fleeing Vietnam, Laos, and Cambodia. Countless died in what came to be known as the “Boat people” crisis.¹⁵¹ When Saigon was captured by the North Vietnamese army, the U.S. had to undertake the most dramatic evacuation in its history, resulting in the arrival of 127,000 Vietnamese families.¹⁵²

Militarized Refuge(es) (2014) by Yen Le Espiritu¹⁵³ entrenches the Vietnam evacuation and resettlement efforts by the U.S. precisely within Necropolitical frameworks. The author hints at the clear militarized nature of the evaluations and the rescues, in an attempt to transform the U.S. military “from violent aggressor in Vietnam to benevolent rescuer of its people”¹⁵⁴, and the protector of Vietnamese peace. Espiritu uses “Militarized refugees” to expose the violence behind the humanitarian narrative of the U.S. military and U.S. government – a narrative which has also been challenged in this research.¹⁵⁵ Unsurprisingly, the author describes the evacuation efforts to have been hasty, unplanned and violent, with few restrictions. This was done, per the author’s claim, as a last-ditch televised stunt for the U.S. military. Although the evacuation phase posed little legal entrapment, the subsequent stages of evacuation and resettlement were, evidently, the instructional itinerary for Necropolitics. This paper will further explore the Afghan migration process regarding the work of Le Espiritu.

4.2.2 *The Rite of passage*

The Rite of passage is the ceremonial institution of celebrating an individual’s transformation. For an Afghan migrant, the transformation is the process of migration, and the rite of passage is the legal framework that constitutes their departure from Afghanistan – the rights of livability. These legal frameworks were drafted and passed by the U.S. Congress in 2008, in the form of a Special Immigration Visa (SIV) to protect Iraqi collaborators who had aided the U.S. armed forces and official personnel. The following year, the SIV program was extended to also cover the Afghans who were considered under threat danger due to their cooperation with the U.S..

In the first iteration of the SIV program, an applicant must have served “for at least one year as translators or interpreters, or who were employed by, or on behalf of, the U.S. government in Afghanistan, and whose lives were threatened because of their work in support of the U.S. mission.”¹⁵⁶ While the SIV was ought to protect “U.S. allies”, the vagueness of what defined an ally created a void

¹⁵¹ Ibid.

¹⁵² Laura Harjanto and Jeanne Batalova, “Vietnamese Immigrants in the United States,” migrationpolicy.org, October 15, 2021, <https://www.migrationpolicy.org/article/vietnamese-immigrants-united-states>.

¹⁵³ Yen Le Espiritu, *Body Counts the Vietnam War and Militarized Refuge(Es)* (Berkeley: University of California Press, 2014).

¹⁵⁴ Ibid.

¹⁵⁵ Ibid.

¹⁵⁶ Human Rights First, “Fact Sheet: The Afghan Special Immigrant Visa Program,” 2019, https://doi.org/https://www.humanrightsfirst.org/sites/default/files/Afghan-SIV-Fact-Sheet_2.pdf.

for the military personnel and those employed by U.S. military contractors. Per the experience of the informants, those who were employed by the likes of Textron and their subsidiaries were expected to undergo a different visa acquisition process. Per the legislative history of the SIV, every fiscal year a certain quota of visas was allocated to the SIV, regardless of the number of individuals employed by the U.S. forces. In 2018, when the major withdrawal of U.S. soldiers from Afghanistan began¹⁵⁷ more Afghans began applying for the SIV program. According to a joint report by the U.S. Department of State and the Department of Homeland Security,¹⁵⁸ In the same period, 14,500 visas were allocated for the program, while 33,727 eligible Afghans had applied for the program.

Establishing outweighed quotas construed to be the first entrapment of the SIV program. The second entrapment, which prolonged the state of limbo for the applicant, was the absurdly long processing time. To obtain the visa, an applicant must have undergone 14 steps and a minimal processing time of 692 days, roughly 1 year and 11 months. The process includes reviews by the Chief of Mission (COM) department, which would confirm the initial application to the National Visa Center (NVC). After 240 processing days, if all documents are presented correctly, the applicants must individually apply to the Department of Homeland Security (DHS) using the I-360 form, consisting of 19 pages that amalgamate 15 different visa categories. Informants were warned that at any stage of filling in wrong information, the candidates must have resubmitted the application from the first processing stage. Upon the application approval by NVC and DHS, the applicant would receive another series of applications to fill in the classified information regarding their operational work and their endangered status in Afghanistan. After 3 days of document reviews, the applicant was given an interview appointment at the U.S. embassy's consular in Kabul after 243 days. Following the interview, the application would undergo an administrative process for another 113 days. If the applicant's passport expires within this timeframe, they're required to renew their passport. In principle, had an applicant began the SIV application after the first phase of major U.S. withdrawal from Afghanistan in December 2018, they'd be able to receive their SIV by November 2020. Any Afghan hired within this period would be unable to receive the SIV by the time of the U.S.'s withdrawal in 2021, regardless of their scale of operation.

¹⁵⁷ Dan Lamothe et al., "Trump Orders Major Military Withdrawal from Afghanistan as Mattis Departs," The Washington Post (WP Company, December 21, 2018), https://www.washingtonpost.com/world/national-security/trump-agitating-for-major-military-withdrawal-from-afghanistan-advisers-say/2018/12/20/0c35f874-04a3-11e9-b5df-5d3874f1ac36_story.html.

¹⁵⁸ U.S. Department of State, "Joint Department of State/Department of Homeland Security Report: Status of the Afghan Special Immigrant Visa Program," 2019, https://doi.org/https://travel.state.gov/content/dam/visas/SIVs/Q3-Afghan_SIV_Report_July_2018.pdf.

During the July press conference when President Biden was asked “Why can’t the U.S. evacuate these Afghan translators to the United States to await their visa processing as some immigrants at the southern border have been allowed to do?”,¹⁵⁹ to which he responded:

*“Because the law doesn’t allow that to happen. And that’s why we’re asking the Congress to consider changing the law. But in the meantime, we can guarantee their safety, if they wish to leave, by taking them to third countries and/or, while the wait is taking place, to come to — to — and hopefully, while they’re waiting there, to be able to bring them back to the United States, if that’s what they choose to do. We’re conducting thorough security screening in the intermediate stops they’re making for anyone who is not a U.S. citizen or a lawful permanent resident of the United States. Anyone arriving in the United States will have undergone a background check. And — and we must all work together to resettle thousands of Afghans who ultimately qualify for refugee status. The United States will do our part. And we are already working closely with refugee organizations to rebuild a system that was purposefully destroyed by my predecessor.”*¹⁶⁰

In deconstructing the response of President Biden, the congressional change occurred under the Afghan Allies Protection Act of 2019 of the 116th Congress. The amendments to this act will be examined in the subsequent section.

The third countries refer to Qatar, and Germany, where U.S.’s military bases would act as externalized territories and cages to contain the Afghans during their immigration processing. The Afghans were also encouraged to move to any other third country to reach the U.S. embassy to process their SIV – with the only option being Pakistan. Moving refugees to the military bases echoes what Le Espiritu denoted as Militarized Refuge referring to the evacuation of the Vietnamese. She believed this revealed a hidden “colonial and militarized nature of these evacuations”¹⁶¹ with the pattern being the airlift of refugees from Saigon to the Philippines, Guam, Thailand, Wake Island, Hawaii, and further distributions across military bases across the U.S..¹⁶² Le Espiritu concluded the militarization of refuge was the construct the narrative of “Good Refuge”, the U.S. turning the Vietnam War into a “Good War” – “an ultimately necessary and moral war.”¹⁶³

¹⁵⁹ The White House Press

¹⁶⁰ Ibid.

¹⁶¹ Espiritu. p.25

¹⁶² Ibid.

¹⁶³ Ibid.

Espiritu further touched on the topic of sovereignty, with that the nature of the evacuations and their selected destinations, was a colonial pattern to reinforce American presence and control over its historical pacific dominions – Philippines, Guam, and Hawaii. Following Espiritu’s position, we can draw a parallel to the third theory which stated the subjects’ survivability dependence on the sovereign, is conceptualized as Necropeon, where the Necropeon unconditionally serves and strengthens the sovereign’s consolidation within internal and externalized territories. In the same pretense, we may interpret the Vietnamese migrants to embody the concept of Necropeon, if their mobility and movement, bound to the U.S.’s coordination, was a reimagination of colonial consolidation of a sovereign.

President Biden’s mention of giving refuge to those qualified as refugees is another repetition of the Vietnam evacuations. The U.S. processes applicants in multiple interview and profile examinations, and only resettles those who have been qualified for refugee status. Although I was not able to reach informants who had the migration process rejected while being caged in a third country, we may extrapolate the potential outcome for those individuals by reflecting on the Vietnam evacuations. According to Espiritu’s research, “Those who could establish past persecution were entitled to resettlement in third countries; those who could not be deemed “economic migrants” and repatriated to Vietnam.”¹⁶⁴ By 1996, of the 120,000 screened Vietnamese candidates, 27% were ultimately qualified for refugee status –as uttered by President Biden– and 63%, about 75,000 were repatriated.¹⁶⁵

A similar process follows the militarized refugees and survival migrants who have already been brought to the U.S. military. In the case of the Vietnamese evacuees, those who were accepted as refugees were granted resettlement. For the “Leftover” refugees rejected from the program, as Espiritu dubs them, “ [they] became stateless peoples who languished in closed camps or detention centers for extended periods without the juridical protection of citizenship.”¹⁶⁶ Ultimately, as my third theory constituted, relinquishing individual freedom –and per Haddad’s understanding of reciprocal relations of subject and sovereign– consolidates the U.S. sovereignty domestically, by being presented as the “other”.

Conveniently for the U.S. Neo-neo policymakers of the 116th congress, President Trump had previously hampered the SIV program and reduced the number of SIV quotas drastically under the “Muslim Ban”, which was framed under protecting Americans.¹⁶⁷ Under the Biden administration, the quota didn’t change until the 117th congress was pressured to do so to speed up the evacuation process,

¹⁶⁴ Ibid. p.54

¹⁶⁵ Ibid.

¹⁶⁶ Ibid. p.59

¹⁶⁷ Mark C. Storella, “How Trump Broke the System That Offers Protection to Afghan Allies,” *The Hill* (The Hill, August 31, 2021), <https://thehill.com/opinion/national-security/570076-how-trump-broke-the-system-that-offers-protection-to-afghan-allies/>.

given the processing time –bureaucratic entrapment– was 731 days in early 2021.¹⁶⁸ The Necropolitical framework of refugee treatment in the caging process is analyzed in greater depth in the next section.

4.2.3 Policy In Practice

Afghan Allies Protection Act of 2009 (AAPA) represents an umbrella body of laws and policies the US congress has been using to constitute what we've argued as Necropolitical. This section studies this protection act along with its evolution through related bills, to further strengthen the claims for the second and the third theories.

The 115th congress, under President Trump's administration, set the prelude to the bureaucratic entrapments and a dead-end policy for the SIV program, by introducing a key deadline for eligible Afghans. The Afghan Allies Protection Amendments Act of 2018¹⁶⁹ set December 31, 2021, as the deadline for the employment period of Afghan collaborators, referred to as aliens in the bill's body. The same date would be the deadline of final eligible applications for the SIV program.

Although it's vaguely hinted at, we may interpret this key date as the determining means to reduce the capacities of the SIV program for future applicants. The bill set a deadline for eligible individuals and for the employability period – ergo, anyone employed after January 1st, 2021 would be dubbed ineligible, given they'd have less than a year of employment. An informant employed in logistics, described experiencing “a jolt of paralyzing shock” when she learned of her ineligibility in April 2021, having worked for 9 months in the U.S. Military. She described, that applying for a visa was a prolonged process of navigating the website for Citizenship and Immigration services with a labyrinth of links and forms. She was employed in the military at the age of 21, with “the single hope to leave the country with her parents.” She and another participant who described the same essence of betrayal by the visa program were assured by their contractor months prior, that they were eligible for the SIV through the completion of their contract in December 2021.

There was no change in the visa policy until August 2nd, 2021, mere two weeks before the fall of Kabul, when the P-2 visa program was introduced to include those whose working terms didn't qualify them for the SIV.¹⁷⁰ As of the time of writing this, certain individuals who applied for the P-2 program in September 2021, have not yet obtained their visa – being in a state of limbo within U.S.'s hyper-externalized territories.

¹⁶⁸ Ibid.

¹⁶⁹ Congress.gov. "S.2793 - 115th Congress (2017-2018): Afghan Allies Protection Amendments Act of 2018." May 7, 2018. <https://www.congress.gov/bill/115th-congress/senate-bill/2793>.

¹⁷⁰ U.S. Department of State, “U.S. Refugee Admissions Program Priority 2 Designation for Afghan Nationals - United States Department of State,” U.S. Department of State (U.S. Department of State, January 28, 2022), <https://www.state.gov/u-s-refugee-admissions-program-priority-2-designation-for-afghan-nationals/>.

The first bill introduced to the senate by the 116th congress in the frame of Afghanistan –following the withdrawal agreement with Taliban– was on April 15th.¹⁷¹ The bill provided minor amendments to the AAPA, by allocating a mere 4,000 additional visa allocations for the SIV program, in addition to the unused allotments from 2015 through 2017 - 0. This extended the visa allotments from 18,500 to 22,500. During the same period, Congressional Research Service reports¹⁷² 18,314 foreigners and host nationals were employed in Afghanistan, the second highest record since 2016.¹⁷³ With discrepant numbers, the SIV program barely provided additional quota for immediate families of contractors.

4.2.4 Marketing On Misery

Another form of sovereign consolidation through necropeonage is the use of policy making efforts as a medium to garner entrenched democratic support. A repeated theme noted during the policy analysis, was the use of gregarious names for policies to enrich marketing and promotional efforts, ultimately taking advantage of the electoral values. The following bills were among the only bills introduced during the period of evacuation and withdrawal which posited minimal practicality, while fully serving the policymakers –sovereigns– as marketing tools. I posit this is a form of necropeonage, under two observations: Firstly, the policies do not challenge the neuropolitical framework or contribute to the relief of the migrants from the “slow-death”. Secondly, the maintenance of the migrants under necropolitical conditions –through inaction– positively serves the policy makers to consolidate their democratic support. This was evident given the press associated with the introduced bills, and my interpretation that more effort was invested in creating marketable acronyms, than producing pragmatic resolutions.

The bill, Emergency Security Supplemental Appropriations Act , passed on July 31, 2021¹⁷⁴ provided additional amendments to the AAPA in an unexpected turn – to add a bureaucratic layer and restrictions for the SIV program, by requiring the candidates to undergo medical examination, prior to obtaining the SIV. A curiously-named bill, “HOPE for Afghan SIVs act of 2021”,¹⁷⁵ or “Honoring Our Promises through Expedition for Afghan”, amended the previously introduced bil, not by extending the SIV quotas, but by rather removing the medical examination step, for until after the applicants had arrived in the U.S.. Essentially the bill named as HOPE, grounded no additional provisions for the

¹⁷¹ Congress.gov. "S.1474 - 116th Congress (2019-2020): Afghan Allies Protection Act of 2019." May 15, 2019. <https://www.congress.gov/bill/116th-congress/senate-bill/1474>.

¹⁷² Congressional Research Services, “Department of Defense Contractor and Troop Levels in Afghanistan and Iraq: 2007-20202021,” February 2021, <https://doi.org/https://sgp.fas.org/crs/natsec/R44116.pdf>.

¹⁷³ Ibid.

¹⁷⁴ Congress.gov. "H.R.3237 - 117th Congress (2021-2022): Emergency Security Supplemental Appropriations Act, 2021." July 30, 2021. <https://www.congress.gov/bill/117th-congress/house-bill/3237>.

¹⁷⁵ Congress.gov. "H.R.3385 - 117th Congress (2021-2022): HOPE for Afghan SIVs Act of 2021." November 9, 2021. <https://www.congress.gov/bill/117th-congress/house-bill/3385>.

Afghan migrants. This phenomenon of introducing policies with gregarious names and little practical impact creates a facade of humanitarianism in easing the migration process – while preserving the status quo. This facade was realized in my research upon further scrutiny of the context surrounding the bill: The phenomena of introducing redundant policies to the congress primarily served the policymakers, who used the Bill as a PR stunt.

Senator Padilla bragged on his website “The HOPE for Afghan SIVs Act will remove one hurdle that prevents them from quickly escaping the dangers they face in Afghanistan due to their service to our troops,”¹⁷⁶ with the reassurance the bill would significantly speed up the visa process for the 20,000 Afghans pending on their visa status.

As we may argue, this is another channel of Afghans' subjection to necropeonage. In this case, the Necropolitical frame is enacted through the inaction of introducing policies with ingenuine biopolitical means. The necropeonage is the domestic consolidation of sovereigns, who use the state of the necropeon in popularizing their democratic support.

The same bill introduces the concept of “conditional permanent resident”. The alien ally, having arrived in the U.S. will obtain conditional permanent residency as a lawfully admitted refugee. The conditions are removed upon the medical examination. Even the slightest amendments ought to ease the migration process and set the migrants in a state of conditional existence.

In totality, none of the informants had complaints about the delay in the medical examination produces in their SIV program. Medical examinations in Afghanistan took less than an hour to complete. The most daunting stages requiring attention were dominantly the processing time before the first interview and after the final interview. Evidently, the greatest obstacle in the speed of processing stages — bound to the resources allocated for the labor. Yet, every relevant bill introduced since the initiation of the withdrawal, either focuses on the quota of available visas or ineffectual processes.

Another bill introduced in the same spirit of redundant practicality and marketing name is the “Save Our Afghan Allies Act”¹⁷⁷ introduced by Senator Kennedy. The bill, which only instructs the Department of Defence to issue a report on wavering visas for eligible Afghans, is introduced on the senator’s website as a “guarantee [Afghans’] protection”¹⁷⁸ The bill, “Showing American Values by

¹⁷⁶ Alex Padilla, “Padilla, Cornyn Introduce Bill to Speed up Immigration Process for Afghan Interpreters Who Assisted US Forces,” Senator Alex Padilla, June 17, 2021, <https://www.padilla.senate.gov/newsroom/press-releases/padilla-cornyn-introduce-bill-to-speed-up-immigration-process-for-afghan-interpreters-who-assisted-us-forces/>.

¹⁷⁷ Congress.gov. "S.2216 - 117th Congress (2021-2022): Save Our Afghan Allies Act." June 24, 2021. <https://www.congress.gov/bill/117th-congress/senate-bill/2216>.

¹⁷⁸ John Kennedy, “Kennedy Introduces Bill to Save America's Afghan Allies from Taliban,” U.S. Senator John Kennedy, June 22, 2021, <https://www.kennedy.senate.gov/public/2021/6/kennedy-introduces-bill-to-save-america-s-afghan-allies-from-taliban>.

Evacuating”,¹⁷⁹ acronymed as SAVE, was lobbied by the veteran support group, With Honor.¹⁸⁰ While the bill made the rudimentary recommendation to provide an additional 10,000 visa allotments to the SIV program, it was marketed on the With Honour’s press as “expands the Special Immigrant Visa program by making clear that those employed under cooperative agreements and grants are eligible for the Afghan SIV program.”¹⁸¹ The majority of the Afghan informants did not care nor were implicitly affected by the visa quotas when the processing time for their applications extended 2 years. Their immediate need, which could be responded to accordingly, was any means to speed up the two processing stages.

The final major bill which passed the house, was “Averting Loss of Life and Injury by Expediting SIVs”¹⁸² – under the acronym ALLIES.¹⁸³ Similar to the aforementioned bills, ALLIES proposed to expand the quota of the SIV visas by 8,000. The bill also unwrapped and deducted a key entrapping clause that I had not paid attention to: eliminating the “requirement that the duties performed qualify as sensitive and trusted duties”¹⁸⁴ as one of the eligibility conditions for the SIV program. It was never defined what encompassed sensitive and trusted duties, and it remains unclear whether it was inclusive of the works of logistics, interpreters, security forces, or others who risked their safety by collaborating with the U.S. forces. The bill additionally eliminated the SIV requirement of providing sworn statements of the threat faced by the applicants. While the amendments proposed by the bill clear the ambiguities and entrapping clauses regarding key conditions of eligibility -which were open to interpretation- it failed to propose effective measures and procedures to speed up the SIV program and the screening process. Yet, it was commended on by the Executive Office as to “assist in our efforts to streamline the application process.”¹⁸⁵

It’s reasonable to contend, that given that the screening process provides the spatial (cabin and third countries) and the temporal conditions for the sovereign to exercise necropeonage, it most accurately embodies the necropolitical frameworks of migration. The next section explores this necropolitical frame through the experiences of the migrants and their relations to their host sovereign.

¹⁷⁹ Congress.gov. "H.R.5134 - 117th Congress (2021-2022): Showing American Values by Evacuating (SAVE) Afghan Partners Act of 2021." August 31, 2021. <https://www.congress.gov/bill/117th-congress/house-bill/5134>.

¹⁸⁰ With Honor Press, “With Honor Action Praises Inclusion of Key 2022 National Defense Authorization Act Amendments,” With Honor, September 27, 2021, <https://withhonor.org/with-honor-action-praises-inclusion-of-key-2022-national-defense-authorization-act-amendments/>.

¹⁸¹ Ibid.

¹⁸² Congress.gov. "H.R.3985 - 117th Congress (2021-2022): Averting Loss of Life and Injury by Expediting SIVs Act of 2021." July 22, 2021. <https://www.congress.gov/bill/117th-congress/house-bill/3985>.

¹⁸³ Congress.gov. "H.R.3985 - 117th Congress (2021-2022): Averting Loss of Life and Injury by Expediting SIVs Act of 2021." July 22, 2021. <https://www.congress.gov/bill/117th-congress/house-bill/3985>.

¹⁸⁴ Ibid.

¹⁸⁵ Executive Office of the President, “Statement of Administration Policy H.R. 3985 – Averting Loss of Life and Injury by Expediting SIVs Act of 2021,” n.d., <https://doi.org/https://www.whitehouse.gov/wp-content/uploads/2021/07/HR3985.SAP-Final.pdf>.

4.3. Katabasis

The phenomenon of Afghan migration is in an inherently katabatic narrative – a journey to the underworld, land of the dead. Necropolitical frameworks which subject Afghans to the condition of slow decay and necropeonage enforce tremendous physical, mental, and emotional strain per the participants' experience. Most frequently expressed a sense of betrayal by the U.S. all while depending on the U.S.'s support for liveability. Being “left behind”, being “left in a limbo” and “wishing to be dead” along with the juxtaposition of “doing anything to keep my family safe” were the essences experienced by the Afghans under the necropolitical frameworks of the SIV program – the rite of passage. This section explores the Afghan's descent to the underworld of migration from the narrative of the participants.

4.3.1 Domestic Decay

When the Trump administration announces the withdrawal of U.S. Military from Afghanistan, the public was divided on its stance. With the majority of the provinces still being under Taliban control after 20 years of warfare, many had lost faith in the U.S.'s ability to stabilize the country. Some of the participants expressed hope of building stability through dialogue and diplomacy with the Taliban. Even among the government officials, some opted to include the Taliban within the constitutional framework of Afghanistan as a democratically elected political party.

Those with military background or connection to government, military and security personnel posited a far more pessimistic stance. These were among the first people who began planning their migration out of Afghanistan following President Trump's announcement. These individuals carried a live memory of Taliban persecution, and were vehemently opposed to the withdrawal decision and a settlement resolution. Although they believed their position and background would set them as a target for the Taliban, they were not qualified to apply for the SIV program, exclusively made for those employed by the U.S. Military. Unable to apply for the SIV program, this group of people felt lured into the promising security and governmental position. They believed their cooperation with the U.S. forces would be a bridge for them and their relatives to eventually leave Afghanistan. They insisted that the U.S. was responsible for the impending Taliban carnage against them – to leave them without protection was equated to a death sentence. Participants compared the situation in Afghanistan to that of Libya, Syria and Iraq – where U.S.'s interventions left the countries in a precarious situation and nullified accountability for the U.S..

The logic was constructed as such: the U.S. created a space of employment for those who would have possibly been targeted by the Taliban: government positions, security positions, activists, etc. By

providing labor for this space, the individuals would set themselves under U.S.'s protection and support. Without the U.S.'s infrastructural support, this space would collapse over those who were providing labor. Afghan security was crippled by rampant corruption and the phenomenon of "Ghost soldiers".¹⁸⁶ The sufficient special security was bound to the U.S.'s sovereign protection. We may argue those who had set themselves a target for the Taliban through cooperation with the U.S. forces, even outside the SIV framework, were subjected to an inevitable act of necropeonage.

Two groups who were shocked of the ineligibility of the SIV program, were those who had not filled the minimum employment period for the U.S. military, those who had worked with U.S. contractor mercenaries without the awareness of the contractor's dissociation with the U.S. military, the activists and journalists who participated in U.S. funded programs, and the security personnel who were employed by the Afghan government, and worked in close proximity with the U.S. forces. The latter group was particularly shocked by the inconsistencies of SIV allocations. Some of their colleagues in senior positions were quickly given the SIV, without the processing time and without a direct contact with the U.S. Military. Although they provided limited tangible proof, they were ardent and they had bribed their way into getting the SIV. Per Mbembe's colonial understanding of Necropolitics, the closer proximity to the power secured the livability of the individuals.

On August 2nd, 29 days before the full U.S. withdrawal from Afghanistan, U.S. introduced U.S. Refugee Admissions Program Priority 2 (P-2 Visa), as an inclusive measure to evacuate those who had been employed by any U.S. affiliated organization, or those who didn't fulfill the minimum employment period for the SIV program. The P-2 program did little assistance to those in desperate need of evacuation, since it functioned through testimonials and referrals. None of the interview participants had applied for the P-2 program due to its convoluted legal conundrum. Every city that was taken over by the Taliban had experienced power outages and network disconnection for about 2-3 weeks. Within the span of this time, the applicants had very limited opportunity to contact any U.S. institution for referrals. As discussed in the previous chapter, the P-2 program could be interpreted as another policy that was legislated for the facade of care and support with minimal practicality for the Survival Migrant – policies of inaction.

For those who were eligible to apply for the SIV, the entrapment experience began from merely navigating the U.S. migration services online. The hotline created for the SIV applicant by the U.S. consulate in Kabul was overwhelmed with the number of applicants calling to check the status of their SIV application. None of the interview participants managed to outwait the hotline queue – some mentioned waiting for more than two hours before reluctantly giving up. When the Operational Allies Welcome began to airlift SIV holders, those with pending applications had little hope. They were

¹⁸⁶ CITE

explicitly told they must wait for their application's processing either in Afghanistan or a third-country. When asked if this process felt like a deliberate delay, or a slowed death sentence, participants universally affirmed this sensation.

4.3.2 Operation Allies Refuge

SIV holders were badged with a barcoded wristband they must have carried to pass the evacuation checkpoint.¹⁸⁷ This process is in parallel to the biometric nominal identifications Davies described the African migrants had to undergo in Italy. The supposedly biopolitical technology that ought to be used to create legal avenues for the migrants, was later used as a means of targeted exclusion of the individuals who strayed outside the legal entrapments of migration. Just as the work of Espiritu compared the U.S. evacuation of Saigon to a colonial process of displacing subjects, I contend to draw another colonial analogy by parallelizing the barcoded badges to the copper badges U.S. used in identifying the freed slaves.¹⁸⁸

Badges were used as a means to disintegrate a community from within – a symbolic policy of creating new dividing lines of identity between a homogenous group. The SIV recipients were badged and identified as the subjects of the sovereign, whereas the swarm of people with pending SIV applications and those ineligible to receive it were identified as the “other”. Referencing the work of Haddad, the badge could act as the artifact that marks the propriety of the sovereign over the individuals. Furthermore, we may also interpret badging of individuals during a migration process as the decoupling of one's ontological human identity, from their capacity to live. The badge dehumanizes the subjects in the lines of liveable and unlivable – regardless of their ontic experiences.

After the enactment of the 3985 - ALLIES bill, the SIV applicants with pending applications were also allowed to access the airport. Those with pending applications described the process as dreadful, as they first had to pass a checkpoint operated by the joint world of the Taliban and the Afghan security forces. Some described the process of even finding the checkpoint as a physical maze with no way to get in or get through the checkpoints. Yet, some were able to bypass the checkpoints by jumping the fences or finding a new avenue to access the evacuation space. Participants describe density in the atmosphere. By virtue of the February deal the U.S. signed with the Taliban, the group reserved the sovereign authority to decide who passed the first checkpoints and who didn't. Participants recall fear of having their names and identities separately listed by the Taliban in a hitlist. A participant working extensively with the security forces described choosing to go to the airport in the very early hours of

¹⁸⁷ Aykut Karadag, “Wristband Barcodes Used for US Evacuations from Afghan Capital,” Anadolu Ajansı, accessed May 15, 2022, <https://www.aa.com.tr/en/asia-pacific/wristband-barcodes-used-for-us-evacuations-from-afghan-capital/2343988>.

¹⁸⁸ Smithsonian Magazine, “This Rare Copper Badge Tells a Story of Slavery in 19th-Century Charleston,” Smithsonian.com (Smithsonian Institution, June 24, 2021), <https://www.smithsonianmag.com/smart-news/slave-badge-found-charleston-180978055/>.

the morning, since he felt the Taliban gatekeepers didn't process rigid screening of identities. The same participant recalled having a number of his colleagues choosing to move to Iran and then Turkey to process the SIV application, with the hopes to bypass the Taliban's hitlist radar. Granting the Taliban sovereign control over the initial evacuation checkpoints could be interpreted as another layer of entrapment. Those affected by this layer, would resort to other means of leaving the territories of Afghanistan – inadvertently undermining the Taliban's sovereign regime in Afghanistan, and creating further liveability dependence on the U.S.

The participants who were present in the airport in the last days of August were not SIV applicants or SIV holders. Many were regular Afghans fearing targeted persecution due to their job as social media personalities, journalism, activism, or family connections with SIV holders – including distant families. These individuals were held back behind the gates by the joint operation of Afghan security forces, U.S. forces and the Taliban.

Operation Allies Welcome incorporated the most complex airlift mission since the evacuation of Saigon. Those who were permeated through the previous legal and physical filters of migration, were airlifted from Hamid Karzai airport to Al Udeid Air Base in Qatar, Ramstein Airbase in Germany, and then to the U.S. Dulles airport, before being distributed between seven militarized bases across the U.S. The subsequent chapters describe the experience of the participants in the Ramstein Airbase, and those who were incorporated into the militarized refuge and caging across the U.S. bases in Quantico, and Holloman Airbase. The abstraction of the experiences and the analysis of the Vietnam evacuation as a precedent are indicative of how the U.S.'s policies of mobility and movement could be interpreted as a mean to operationalize the necropolitical framework. The results conform to the third theory, which reinforces the notion that the policies of movements for the migrants served to reinforce to sovereign consolidation of the U.S. within its territorial and externalized borders.

4.3.3 Militarized Migration

Citing the works of Fitzgerald, third countries in the refugee migration processes function as buffer zones and externalized territories. To Espiritu, the tracing of the evacuation route revealed a reinforcement of U.S. colonial subordination of the historical pacific holdings – a hyper-externalization of sovereignty and its consolidation. The externalized territories which caged the migrants were all active U.S. military bases. Espiritu hints “The material and ideological conversion of U.S. military bases into places of refuge—places that were meant to resolve the refugee crisis, promising peace and protection—discursively transformed the United States from violent aggressor in Vietnam to benevolent rescuer of its people”¹⁸⁹ She further traces this process to the conversion of German

¹⁸⁹ Espiritu, p.35

Concentration camps to “Assembly Centres” for refugees in postwar Europe.¹⁹⁰ Seeing the precedent of this phenomenon, I argue this process of reconstructing the image of the U.S. military bases as necessary establishments for assisting refugees, reinforces the importance of their presence in the third country territories – thus, embodying another form of consolidating externalized sovereignty.

The migration route for the Afghan evacuees connected two critically important U.S. airbases in the Middle East and Europe – Al Udeid and Ramstein airbase. Tracing the migration route concerning the work of Espiritu reveals probable intentions to reconstruct the image of these bases from a military launching pad against U.S. adversaries to an indispensable humanitarian corridor. An operationalization of which entails controlling the movement of migrants – laboring their necro peonage.

The Saigon evacuation analog to Al Udeid and Ramstein air bases is Clark AFB, which was the “backbone of logistical support for U.S. involvement in Southeast Asia,”¹⁹¹ which was the headquarters for the U.S. forces active in the entire Asia-Pacific.¹⁹² Linking Clark AFB with other U.S. bases during the evacuation, was a reaffirmation of militarism in the pacific territories under the facade of a refugee corridor.¹⁹³

Examining the operational history of the Al Udeid and Ramstein Airbases reveals the importance of the two sites to the U.S. 's militarism and reinforced externalized territories. The Al Udeid airbase was the launching pad of Operation Desert Storm in 1991 which expelled Iraq from Kuwait and crippled its army from posing a threat against the Persian Gulf oil & gas reservoirs, tankers and facilities. Nowadays, the facility being the host to the largest American base,¹⁹⁴ enacts as a repellent against Iran, which contends to challenge the arguably de facto militaristic hegemony of the U.S. over the region. With every stroke of tension, the base is used by the U.S. military to counter any Iranian intent of jeopardizing the U.S.'s position in the region.¹⁹⁵ Similarly, the Ramstein Airbase was deliberately designed as a NATO command center, while today acting as a multinational headquarter to the Allied Air Forces Central Europe.¹⁹⁶ Most recently, the Airbase hosted the International Advisory Group on

¹⁹⁰ Ibid. p.36

¹⁹¹ Ibid.

¹⁹² Ibid.

¹⁹³ Ibid. p.37

¹⁹⁴ Adam Taylor, “As Trump Tries to End 'Endless Wars,' America's Biggest Mideast Base Is Getting Bigger,” The Washington Post (WP Company, August 23, 2019),

https://www.washingtonpost.com/world/as-trump-tries-to-end-endless-wars-americas-biggest-mideast-base-is-getting-bigger/2019/08/20/47ac5854-bab4-11e9-8e83-4e6687e99814_story.html.

¹⁹⁵ Oriana Pawlyk, “F-22s Deploy to Qatar for the First Time amid Iran Tensions,” Military.com, June 28, 2019, <https://www.military.com/daily-news/2019/06/28/f-22s-deploy-qatar-first-time-amid-iran-tensions.html>.

¹⁹⁶ Allied Air Command Public Affairs Office, “NATO Air Chiefs Meet in Ramstein ‘Our Job Is to Ensure We Maintain Alliance Sovereignty,’” [ac.nato.int](https://ac.nato.int/archive/2022/NACS_22_1), accessed May 15, 2022, https://ac.nato.int/archive/2022/NACS_22_1.

Ukraine's counteraction to Russia and a point of command for coordinated military assistance and reinforcement for the country.¹⁹⁷

By reinforcing Espiritu's militarized refuge to the case of Afghan migration, we find a recurring pattern of coordinating the movement of migrants between military bases with regional significance to arguably consolidate the U.S.'s presence within its hyper-externalized territories – the third country. This process of laboring the existence of the migrants to consolidate sovereignty fulfills the rationale of the third theory – Necropeons being unconditionally employed to serve and strengthen the sovereign's consolidation within internal and externalized territories.

4.3.4 Caged In Living Hell

Nearly the entirety of Operation Allies Refuge relied on remote control policies to contain the majority of the Afghan migrants. Only after the Al Udeid and Ramstein bases over capacitated the evacuation engaged U.S.-based military bases to host SIV applicants and other evacuated refugees. The leaked memo accessed by Axios, described the living conditions in Al Udeid as a "Living hell."¹⁹⁸ This correlated with how the participants who spent weeks there described the situation. The over capacitated cage provided the minimum hospitality apparatus.

After holding an in-depth interview with a resident who shared a controversial Facebook post about the camp, it was evident that the facility's primary concern was to act as a containment. Lack of Air Conditioning, toilets, showers, poor hygiene, and infestation of rats and pests infuriated the residents. The informant described many were regretful about leaving Afghanistan, believing in all sincerity they would've received better treatment by the Taliban. When asked when they were expecting to be transferred to the U.S. bases and Ramstein, the informant confirmed it depended on the stage application process. The informant further added they "don't know yet" whether they'd be repatriated back to Afghanistan if the SIV application fails, while "[they] expect it." The case of repatriation would have acted as a relief measure in the inhuman conditions which constrained the expectedly biopolitical institution tantamount to "living hell". The condition of confining refugees to this state of bare-life was also echoed by Espiritu, describing the livability conditions as "crammed together behind chain link fences topped with barbed wire and patrolled by prison authorities, refugees in closed camps were not allowed to go beyond the boundaries set by the wired fences."¹⁹⁹

¹⁹⁷ John A. Tirpak, "Long-Term Ukraine Aid to Be Discussed at Ramstein Meeting," Air Force Magazine, April 24, 2022, <https://www.airforcemag.com/long-term-ukraine-security-to-be-discussed-at-ramstein-meeting/>.

¹⁹⁸ Hans Nichols and Jonathan Swan, "'A Living Hell': Leaked Email Describes Squalid Afghan Refugee Conditions," Axios, August 24, 2021, <https://www.axios.com/2021/08/24/afghan-refugees-conditions-qatar>.

¹⁹⁹ Espiritu, p.63

The process of caging as a remote control also provided authority to the U.S. to repatriate evacuated Afghans with failed SIV applications, without invoking the Non-refoulement principle of International Human Rights law concerning refugees – regardless of the cage is an externalized territory. Most changes and improvements in the camp were credited to the initiative of the U.S. Military. After assessing every proposed and passed policy during this period of evacuation, the only consistent theme was a form of *inaction* which reduced the liveability of the refugees to the state of “living hell.” The policies enacted during this period by the U.S. failed to address the horrid situation in the Al Udaid camp, living conditions, or the SIV processing time. Although I intended to use posthuman performativity to assess the dynamic of policy-practice relations, the observations confirmed little policy dynamics in response to the field circumstances.

While none of the participants was aware of any case of repatriation, Axios reported the first case on March 1, 22, where an Afghan with an unclear criminal record was set to return to Afghanistan.²⁰⁰ This sets a precedent to flag unwanted individuals for future deportations. Per the original agreement signed between the U.S. and the Taliban in February, the Taliban –and not the Afghan government– were to be fully responsible for the resettlement of the repatriated individuals, otherwise the deportees. Thus, the U.S. 's agreement had created the anticipated infrastructure of deportations.

For the SIV applicants who were cleared to move to the U.S., the settlement process posed a different set of challenges, which still kept the individuals at the risk of deportation or transfer to a detention center. For the Vietnamese migrants, this was the case for those who had failed the screening and the interview processes. Espiritu describes the screening process as a mystery for the refugees, “they debated at great length over what to say and how to behave, offering and soliciting advice from each other on the “magic words” that would gain them a resettlement offer”²⁰¹ By virtue of the internet and modern telecommunications, Afghans used various Whatsapp groups, Facebook pages and telegram channels to provide support on the SIV application, including sharing interview questions. Some described using assistance from the International Refugee Assistance Project (IRAP) to prepare for the interviews. The interview process would often take about an hour if it included the family members, and did not pose considerable constraint over the Afghan applicants.

4.3.5 Settlement

The experience of those who were transported to the U.S. varied depending on the proximity of their closeness to their U.S. contractor. For instance, interpreters who worked directly with the U.S. forces in the field and had received the SIV, were quickly introduced to settlement organizations to

²⁰⁰ Stef W. Kight, “U.S. Departs First Afghan Back to Afghanistan,” Axios, March 1, 2022, <https://www.axios.com/2022/03/01/afghan-deportation-afghanistan-ice-immigration-taliban>.

²⁰¹ Espiritu. p.54

incorporate them into their communities. Others who had received the SIV, and those with pending SIV who lacked linguistic fluency, were kept in the cages across various U.S. Military and Air bases. For those who had received the SIV, they would be kept until they had been indoctrinated to the American way of living. Special educational classes included subjects such as credit score system, daylight savings, democracy, elections, and the history of the United States.

Espiritu described this process of indoctrination as a mean to train refugees for asylum in the West, while also persuading them to “internalize the values and hierarchies of the United States and to transform them into particular kinds of modern human beings (bound for Western liberal democracies).”²⁰² To a number of assessed U.S. media outlets, this process was broadcasted with positive connotation and driving a particular narrative: That the migrants were being trained to be Americans, no longer being the “others”, per Haddad’s categorization. The narrative enforced the impression that the Afghans were finally settling in their new home, thankful to the Americans and the U.S. military.²⁰³²⁰⁴²⁰⁵ The dehumanizing and desensitizing experience of the migrants was translated into the compassion and benevolence of the sovereign.

For those who also had pending SIV applications, they would undergo the same classes with less intensity. To the latter group of people, their status and future hanged in the balance of their SIV application results. Participants expressed unsure of where they’d go to had the applications been rejected. If the U.S. government chooses to act on the precedent of the processes Vietnamese refugees followed, the fate of rejected Afghan migrants is the migrationdetention centers, which were first and foremost were constructed to reinforce the policies introduced under the framing of American security.

Despite the diversity in demographics and professional background the migrant community possesses, they’re united by having moved to the U.S. in rags and with little substantial assets. The process of morphing from the “others” identity to the identity of the subjects homogenized by the sovereign, indebted to those who’ve been granted settlement permissions. Rather than having the liberty to choose the profession they’d wish to engage in, the participants described being constrained to having “survival jobs” – working in warehouses, janitorial positions, delivery services, and other labors substantiating the survival. Reiterating the Foucauldian term, to live at the mercy of a sovereign state is to be bare-life, ripe for extermination or escapades of the states — the phenomenon of such extent of dependence is another medium of compounding the sovereign authority over the individuals.

²⁰² Ibid. p.60

²⁰³ Washington Post. "Newly arrived Afghan family settles in, but worries about those left behind ". 2021. YouTube, 3:23, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=CfDOG6ZhcS8>.

²⁰⁴ VOA News. "Afghan Refugee Family Is Adjusting to Life in the US". 2021. YouTube, 4:16, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=dg63O59mh9Y>

²⁰⁵ ABC News. "Afghan refugees work to start a new life in the US". 2021. YouTube, 8:11, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=qAviXjrI9IU>

In summary, my research contends the caging and settlement of the migrants facilitates five key services for the deliberate entrenchment of U.S. government's sovereignty within its internal and external territories:

1. Caging fosters the presence of the U.S. government in the third country, and reaffirms the necessity of the military bases as externalized sovereign territories;
2. Caging creates the spatiotemporal requisite for the U.S. government to use policy introduction and policy enactment as means to domestically consolidate its sovereignty;
3. Caging reduces the livability of the migrants to bare-life, thereby increasing their livability dependence on the U.S.
4. Caging conforms the policy frameworks based on protecting the U.S. and the securitization of the screening processes – to filter out the “others” and consolidate domestic sovereignty;
5. Caging provides the space to further homogenized the subjects in conformity with the sovereign

None of these four services function without the involuntary service of the necropeon – a survival migrant whose state of conditional existence has been condemned to the operationalization of necropolitics.

5. Conclusion

Through incorporating interpretive policy analysis, performativity, and ethnography, this research examined the clandestine necropolitical realities of the biopolitical policies of the U.S.. In answering “*How Necropolitics is operationalized in the United States’ migration policy?*”, we first had to theorize the “*why?*” – how the U.S. government could benefit from intrinsically necropolitical migration policies? We established the premise that necropolitical policies are those which curtail individuals’ freedom to bare-life, create spatiotemporal conditions of (un) survivability, and cultivate the phenomena of Necropeonage. Necropeonage is the mode of existence for a Necropeon, an individual who has been subjected to involuntary labor for the matter of survival. By referencing the works of other migration scholars, Haddad and Fitzgerald, the study bases the “*why?*” on a close multiplicative codependent relation between the migrants and the sovereign. Where the sovereign needs to be *needed* to consolidate itself, the migrant reinforces the *need*.

The empirical section yielded a number of key findings. Chronologically, the U.S.'s agreement with the Taliban creates a paradoxical state of sovereign-subject relations between the Afghan, the Afghan government, and the Taliban. By analyzing the domineering of the U.S. over the Afghan government, the paper concluded it to represent the de facto suzerain, and by extension, sovereign over the Afghans. The U.S.'s February agreement with the Taliban would de jure recognize Taliban sovereignty only within the intra-Afghan dialogue and a co-existing government, while paradoxically granting the Taliban responsibilities only anointed to the sovereign – such as issuing passports, providing security, and handling the impending migration and displacement crisis within Afghanistan. The subsequent result was a mishap in the formation of a stable and consolidated government within Afghanistan, which would only result in internal conflict and an impending migration crisis. This conundrum of sovereign-subject relation set the prelude to the operationalization of necropolitics.

By following the odyssey of the migrants, we realized how the existential dread was weaponized/utilized to snare the migrant into the bureaucratic entrapment. This existential threat constructed the phenomenological foundation of necropolitics – the requisite essence to labor the migrants’ sense of survival. The temporal dimension was established through protracting the SIV application process, which was only exacerbated by the influx of applicants following the U.S.'s withdrawal announcement. The spatial infrastructure of necropolitics was constructed through Caging and remote policies within externalized territories. The architecture of this spatiotemporal necropolitical framework provided the U.S. with a variety of means to utilize the migrants and their movements to foster its sovereignty within the internal and external territories.

The first explored means of operationalizing necropolitics was through policy construction. A set of legislated policies before the migration had created a byzantine entrapment for the Afghan survival migrants. Policies that were introduced during and following the migration, contributed little change to the situation in the field. Instead, they acted as promotional tools for policymakers to strengthen their support, or for lobbyists to promote their brand of work. This laboring of the limbo state of migrants was interpreted as the first form of necropeonage – where the migrants exist insofar as to reinforce the sovereignty of the government.

The research further traced the route of evacuations and posited the interpretation that the routes were deliberately chosen to create a humanized narrative for the U.S. Military bases outside the U.S. The bases formerly recognized as launching pads of devastating invasions were instantly transformed into evacuation checkpoints and humanitarian corridors. In this virtue, the U.S. could reinforce its sovereignty over its externalized territories by pointing to substantial necessity and service U.S. bases provide in the third countries – besides invasions.

The remote policies and the policies of screening legislation for the caged immigrants would be used as a means to galvanize domestic support by framing these policies under “American Security”. In the separation of migrants, as the “Others' ’, from the Americans –the bonafide subjects– the U.S. government creates a homogenized space that would require the integration of the refugees. The caging process was used as a medium to indoctrinate the migrants into the American way of life – what we can interpret as the way of being subjected to the sovereign.

In the undertaking of this research, we’ve narrated a myriad of ways in which the U.S. operationalizes the necropolitical framework. Externalization of territories, policy marketing, and domestic homogenization can all be interpreted as the key processes of the U.S.’s consolidation of sovereignty through migration policies. For a closing remark, I’m compelled to draw a reference to the role Civil Society plays in bursting the Hippocratic bubble per Fitzgerald’s remark. The active role of Civil Societies in detecting the spurious facade of humanitarianism over militarized migration is imperative in pressuring the policymakers to take an active stance in protecting the rights of refugees. I sincerely hope the findings of this research contribute to expanding the knowledge architecture of migration policies and migration studies.

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